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* Dept. of Mechatronic Advanced System, *Transilvania University of Brasov*, Romania, e-mail: memanescu@yahoo.ro

** Dept. of Mechatronic Advanced System, *Transilvania University of Brasov*, Romania, e-mail: lcristea@unitbv.ro

*** Dept. of Engineering and Management in Tourism, *Transilvania University of Braşov*, e-mail: danielola@yahoo.com.

ECOTOURISM IN THE STATE OF QUEENSLAND – AUSTRALIA

M. FLOREA*

Abstract: *The state of Queensland, located in the extreme NE Australia is considered to be one of the best places in the world for ecotourism. There are two unique ecosystems: The Great Barrier Reef (the biggest and most diverse area of marine life) and Daintree Forest the oldest rainforest in the world. It is the role of Australian authorities for managing an intense ecotourism in these environments without touching the natural equilibrium.*

Keywords: *ecotourism, Queensland, Australia.*

Introduction

The International Ecotourism Society defines Ecotourism as a "responsible travel to the natural areas that conserves the environment and improves the welfare of local people". The Australian Commission on National Ecotourism Strategy calls it: nature-based tourism that involves education and interpretation of the natural environment and is managed to be ecologically sustainable.

Australia is a vast ancient land populated by a small but modern community. Covering an area as large as Europe, Australia is the largest island continent in the world. Can be considered also as the oldest, flattest and – with the exception of Antarctica – the driest place on earth. Due to its isolation in the southern hemisphere in a tropical climate this huge land preserves unique species of animals (namely marsupials and ancient mammals) and at least two unique landforms: Uluru, the largest monolith in the world and the Great Barrier Reef, the longest coral reef and also the most complex marine ecosystem. But there are many natural attractions which gave birth to one of the most interesting potential for ecotourism.

Each state has natural resources for tourism but we have chosen the state of Queensland where the Australian experience of green tourism could be an excellent example for our own country.

Queensland is Australia's second-largest State, covering 1 727 200 km² in the north-eastern corner of the continent. World-famous natural features have earned Queensland a reputation as a premier holiday destination with

both interstate and international tourists. The most visited natural wonders are:

- **Eastern coast** with a succession of beaches, headlands, lagoons, estuaries and mangrove swamps in a narrow strip between the Pacific Ocean and the Great Dividing Range is the most visited area.. Offshore, the islands and coral reefs of the **Great Barrier Reef** form one of the great wonders of the natural world. Around Cairns, the most visited places are: Lizard Island, Green Island, Fitzroy Island, Dunk Island, Bedarra Island, Hinchinbrook Island, Orpheus Island and Magnetic Island.

- Two thirds of Queensland is located close to the Tropics. The north-east coast is subject to monsoon conditions during the wet period, which runs from November to April. Here are some of the most interesting **wettropical forests** one of these is considered to be the oldest in the world: **Daintree**. The forest preserves many species of rain forest trees, mangroves, flowers and parasite plants. The fauna includes crocodiles, iguanas, many species of parrots, butterflies.

The key to an explosive development of tourism in this area is **Cairns Airport**, the gateway to Queensland wonders. In 1934 the people of Cairns started raising money to build an airport where aircraft were able to land and take off at all times. The Australian Government bought the airport in 1937 for using during World War II. The airport was upgraded in 1949, 1962 and in 1975 was opened for international traffic. Cairns Airport was the first airport in Australia (2009) to be the fully equipped for bar-coded boarding passes. The number of passengers reached more than 3 million for domestic flights and over 564 000- international flights in the financial year 2009/2010. Queensland build its national and international reputations as a leader in sustainable ecotourism due to a the Ecotourism Plan 2003-2008; the plan contains measures for touristic development, management and marketing strategies in order to obtain a high quality touristic product. The priorities are:

- improving the business operating environment and sustainable tourism outcomes for protected area managers and tourism operators accessing protected areas
- providing for improved working relationships between industry and agencies
- addressing issues of Native Title and associated implications for tourism operators accessing protected areas
- encouraging greater Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander involvement in ecotourism industry
- addressing issues of risk management and public liability as they relate to ecotourism
- developing a greater understanding of the nature of the domestic and international ecotourism market
- ensuring the growth projections for ecotourism in Queensland are appropriately considered in the planning and management of the protected area estate.

This Master Plan has specific focuses on touristic *operators* (quality, environmental awareness), *visitors* (education and participation), *Commonwealth Government* (directions at a national level), *Queensland Government* – providing direction for ecotourism at a state and regional level.

There are also included: natural area managers, conservation groups, indigenous people, outdoor recreation stakeholders, educational institutions and other special interest groups – Ecotourism

DOMESTIC PASSENGERS - CAIRNS AIRPORT

INTERNATIONAL PASSENGERS - CAIRNS AIRPORT

Australia, Queensland Tourism Industry Council, Association of Marine Park Tourism Operators, Savannah Ltd (a network of professional tour guides), Green Globe 21 Asia Pacific – a global environmental

certification program for the travel and tourism industry.

The nature and style of the Queensland ecotourism experience is a product of not only the State's variety of natural areas in public and private ownership but also a well established industry that is a market leader in providing ecotourism opportunities that realize the potential of these natural areas.

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BENEFIC EFFECTS OF SEVERALS ESSENTIAL OILS IN HEALTHY AND POTATO VIRUS Y INFECTED PLANTS *Nicotiana tabacum* (cv. WHITE BURLEY)

C. L. BĂ D Ă RĂ, F. DAMȘA, A. MĂRCULESCU, N. COJOCARU, M. IANOȘI

Abstract: Usually, *Nicotiana tabacum* (family *Solanaceae*) is used like test plant for potato virus Y. Antioxidants (rosmarinic acid, chlorogenic acid) presents in essential oils extracted from *Thymus serpyllum*, *Lavandula officinalis* are implicated in the processus signaling against stress. The effects of treatments with these oils (dilution 1/100 and 1/1000) on the plants imunisation level (optic density, absorbance at 405nm value), on the fresh leaves weight (after 90 vegetation days) and on phothosyntetic pigments content were evaluated after virus inoculation. Without oils treatments, PVY inoculated plants suffered significant reductions in leaf weight compared to uninfected controls and to plants treated with essential oils. Concerning the antiviral effect of the *Thymus serpyllum* and *Lavandula officinalis* oils, all the injected plants presented after PVY mechanical inoculation absorbances values at 405nm significantly lower than the untreated and inoculated controls.

Keywords: potato virus Y, *Thymus serpyllum*, *Lavandula officinalis*, essential oils.

Introduction

Obtaining health and safety food impose the improvement of techniques used for pathogen agents control, choosing new opportunities, methods, players, natural resources.

Potato virus Y (PVY) (*Potyviride*) is one of the most important viruses of potato (*Solanum tuberosum* L.) (Ragsdale et al., 2001). High PVY level 7can cause stand loss, reduced yields, undersized tubers and reduced quality (Beemsteret al.,1987). Over the past 20 years, PVY has become an increasingly serious constraint to seed potato production in the world(Davis et al., 2008; Lorenzen, 2006). The efforts to control PVY are essential when producing potatoes for market or seed (Bădărău et al., 2010; Bădărău et al., 2009; Beemsteret al.,1987; Lorenzen et al., 2006). Being very susceptible to potyvirus infection, *Nicotiana tabacum* (family *Solanaceae*) is used usually like test plant for potato virus Y, for researches and experiences with potyviruses (Beemsteret al.,1987).

Plant cells have defensive responses to pathogen attack associated with changes in oxidative metabolism (Hammerschmidt et al., 2005). One of the consequences of stress is an increase in the cellular concentration of reactive oxygen species (ROS), which are ubsequently converted to hydrogen peroxide (H₂O₂). In this

processus, several phenolic compounds and constituents of *Thymus serpyllum*, *Lavandula officinalis* plants (Family *Lamiaceae*, order *Lamiales*) having antioxidant activity and pharmaceutical properties (Petersen, 2001), could play an important role. They are also antimicrobial and antiviral wich protect the plants. Oils extracted from *Thymus serpyllum*, *Lavandula officinalis* introduced in healthy and infected potato plants could be implicated in the process signaling against stress (Triantaphyllou et al., 2001) and in ROS transformations. Also, ROS, particularly H₂O₂, play versatile roles in normal plant physiological processes and in resistance to stress. H₂O₂ produced in excess is harmful, but lower concentrations are beneficial (Quan et al., 2005). Genetic and physiological evidence suggests that H₂O₂ acts as a signaling second messenger, mediating the acquisition of tolerance to both biotic and abiotic stress and providing information about changes in the external environment (Apostol et al., 1998; Quan et al., 2008). For example, exogenous application of H₂O₂ induced tolerance to high temperature (López-Delgado et al., 1998) and to chilling (Mora-Herreraet al., 2005) in microplants of *Solanum tuberosum*. Another molecule that participates in response to both biotic and abiotic stress is ascorbic acid (AA), which acts as an antioxidant, protecting the cell against oxidative stress caused by environmental factors and

¹ National Institute of Research and Development for Potato and Sugar Beet Brașov, e-mail:carmen_badarau@yahoo.com, dms_flory@yahoo.com

pathogens. Changes in AA content can modulate systemic acquired resistance (Noctor, 2006; Pastori et al., 2003). AA is a regulator of cell division, cell elongation and growth (Kerk et al., 1995). Considering that compounds from *Lamiaceae* plants oils have antiviral and antioxidant activity (Bedoux et al., 2010; Triantaphyllou et al., 2001) and that H₂O₂ and AA have been implicated in signaling gene expression against biotic and abiotic stresses (Foyer et al., 2005; Noctor et al., 2006), the objectives of this work were to evaluate the effects of treatments with *Thymus serpyllum*, *Lavandula officinalis* oils, hydrogen peroxide and AA on photosynthetic pigments in healthy and mechanical inoculated tobacco (*Nicotiana tabacum*) plants with potato virus Y (PVY). Another purpose of our researches was to study the antiviral activity of these oils treatments on tobacco plants inoculated with PVY.

Materials and methods

a. Plant material. We used healthy tobacco plants cv. Whyte Burley (transferred to greenhouse conditions 30 days after the emergence) and infected (positive) material PVY inoculated plants (inoculation in the 4 leaves phase), using a secondary infected source potato cv. Record (Bădărău and Mărculescu, 2010). The infection of the material was confirmed by

ELISA tests (after 4 weeks from the inoculation) (figure 1).

b. ELISA test. The antiserum and conjugated used for viruses detection were obtained in our laboratory (Cojocaru et al., 2009). The analysis was performed following essentially the protocol described by Clark and Adams (1977) (100µl). The substrate solution (p-nitrophenylphosphate) incubation time was 1 hour. The absorbance values were estimated at 405 nm (A₄₀₅) on PR1100 reader and samples having A₄₀₅ values exceeding the cut-off (two times the average of healthy controls) were considered virus infected.

c. Plants treatments. The tobacco plants were transplanted to pots and after 10, 20 and 30 days, all the plants (excepting the controls) were injected with *Thymus serpyllum*, *Lavandula officinalis* oil (dilution 1/100; 1/1000) 100µl each plant (figure 1). 7 days after the first injection, the plants were sprayed twice weekly for the next time with 10 mL per plant of either 1 mM H₂O₂ or 3 mM AA at pH 5.6 (Bădărău and Mărculescu, 2010). Controls and plants treated only with natural oil were sprayed with distilled water. Four virus infected (positive) and healthy (negative) plants were sprayed in randomized arrays for each chemical treatment, and each treatment was performed in four independent experiments.

Fig. 1. Plant inoculation with potato virus Y (PVY). Original treatments with essential oils

d. Pigment analysis. Measurements were performed for each experiment on plants, 80 days after the first transplanting. Five leaf discs (about 1.5 cm diameter) per plant were taken from mid-shoot leaves of three plants per treatment. Samples for each assay comprised 15 discs,

homogenized in 4 mL of 80% acetone at 4°C. Insoluble materials were removed by centrifugation at 2500 rpm for 10 min. Chlorophylls a and b, and carotenoids, were analyzed spectrophotometrically according to the method of Lichtenthaler and Wellburn (1983).

Experimental variants

H1 negative controls (untreated and uninfected); V1 positive controls (untreated and infected)

H2+ V2 injected with *T.s.* oil (oil 1) dil 1/100 + chemical treatments

H3 +V3 injected with *T.s.* oil (oil 1) dil 1/1000 + chemical treatments

H4 +V4 injected with *L.o.* oil dil 1/100+ chemical treatments

H5 +V5 injected with *L.o.* oil dil 1/1000+ chemical treatments

(H=healthy; V=infected with potato virus Y)

Fresh weight of leaves were recorded 60 days after the second plants transplanting.

e. Statistical analysis. Data were analyzed by ANOVA and Duncan's Multiple Range Test and scored as significant if $P < 0.05$. In the aim to illustrate the precision of the mean we used the confidence interval (CI).

Results and discussions

a. Treatments effects on photosynthetic pigments.

Effects of treatments with *Thymus serpyllum*, *Lavandula officinalis* oil and H_2O_2 or AA, were compared on pigment contents and fresh weight of both healthy and virus infected (PVY) tobacco plants cv White Burley.

Fig. 2. Chlorophyll a (A) and chlorophyll b (B) of leaves of healthy plants (□) and potato virus Y (PVY) infected plants (▨), following treatments with *Thymus serpyllum* (TS) and *Lavandula officinalis* oil (LO) and spray with H_2O_2 (1mM) or AA (3mM) or water (controls). Data are means \pm SD of four experiments ($n=4$). Errors bars are 95% CI of means. Bars with different letters differ significantly by ANOVA and Duncan's test ($P < 0.05$).

Changes in photosynthetic pigment contents were evaluated 80 days after emergence (Figure 2

A, B). Without chemical treatments, the positive leaves showed significant reductions, compared

to uninfected leaves, in chlorophyll a (by 32%), chlorophyll b (by 57%). Treatments with essential oils, H_2O_2 and AA significantly increased pigment contents of PVY infected plant leaves to levels similar to uninfected plants. Compared with positive controls (untreated and inoculated), in all the variants, the chlorophyll a and chlorophyll b content of inoculated plants

was significantly higher. No significant differences were induced by these treatments in the uninfected plants (Figure 2A ,B). So, after virus inoculation, the plants infected (positive controls) suffered significantly harmful effects. These effects were reduced following the chemical treatments (treated plants).

Fig. 3. **A.** Absorbances (optic density) values at 405nm of healthy (□) and infected (■) *Nicotiana tabacum* plants with potato virus Y(PVY), following treatments with *Thymus serpyllum* and *Lavandula officinalis* oil (dilution 1/100;1/1000) and H_2O_2 (1 mM), AA (3 mM) or water (controls). Data are means \pm SD of four experiments ($n=4$). Bars with different letters differ significantly by ANOVA and Duncan's test ($P<0.05$).

B. Influence of treatments of healthy and inoculated *Nicotiana tabacum* plants with potato virus Y(PVY) on optic density (absorbances) values at 405nm. 95% CI - 95% confidence interval of the difference

b. Treatments effects on plant immunity

Effects of treatments with *Thymus serpyllum*, *Lavandula officinalis* oils and H_2O_2 or AA, were compared on absorbances values obtained after testing (DAS ELISA technique) healthy and

inoculated plants (cv. Whyte Burley) with potato virus Y(PVY).

The antiviral activity of treatments were evaluated 4 weeks after the last transplanting (Figure 3 A&B). Compared with their positive

controls, with chemical treatments, the inoculated plants showed significant decreases of the absorbances values (Figure 3). Treatments with *Thymus serpyllum* oils and H₂O₂ or AA significantly decreased DO_{405nm} of samples prelevated from virus PVY infected plant leaves to levels similar to uninfected. The best results were obtained using the oil's dilution 1/100. No significant differences were induced by these treatments in the uninfected plants (Figure 3A). The *Lavandula officinalis* oils have lower effect on plants immunity compared with *Thymus serpyllum* (Figure 3B).

c. Treatments effects on the fresh weight

The chemical treatments increased the fresh weight in the PVY infected plants compared to their positive control. Reduced weight is one of the characteristic plants answers to STRESS.

Final harvests were carried out at 90 days after emergence. Positive plants treated with *Thymus*

serpyllum oil produced significantly more biomass than the positive controls. All the treatments induced significant differences in the fresh weight in healthy plants (Figure 4). Fresh weights of the uninfected control plants were significantly higher than the positive control (Figure 4). However oil treatments significantly enhanced the weight of plants in the positive plants compared to their control (Figure 4). The treatments with *Lavandula officinalis* oils resulted in plants weights that were either not significantly different to, or greater than those of uninfected controls (Figure 4). Significant incrementation by the chemical treatments of the weight of plants harvested was observed in the uninfected plants compared with their control, this effect remaining significant for the plants treated with *Thymus serpyllum* oil dilution 1/100 (Fig.4)

Fig. 4. Fresh weight of healthy plants (□) and positive-infected plants with potato virus Y(PVY) - (■), following injections with *Thymus serpyllum* (TS) and *Lavandula officinalis* oil (LO) and spray treatments with H₂O₂ (1 mM), AA (3 mM) or water (controls), twice weekly. Data are means ± SD of four experiments (n=4). Error bars are 95% CI of means (95% confidence interval of the difference)

Concerning the antiviral effect of *Thymus serpyllum* and *Lavandula officinalis* oils, all the injected tobacco plants presented after PVY mechanical inoculation absorbances values at 405nm significantly lower than the untreated and inoculated controls. This research demonstrates potential benefits of *Thymus serpyllum* oils on the immunisation of *Nicotiana tabacum*, a good brother of *Solanum tuberosum*

L. Using these oils, the results were amazing, the OD_{405nm} values were significantly decreased.

Hydrogen peroxide is a diffusible molecule and its accumulation is perceived by the plant as a signal of environmental change, alerting the cell to both biotic and abiotic threats (Noctor et al., 2006). It also alters the concentrations and redox status of intracellular antioxidants, such as ascorbate (Foyer et al., 2005). The role of H₂O₂

in the induction of tolerance to stresses in potato plants has been demonstrated. López-Delgado et al. (1998 and 2005) and Mora-Herrera et al. (2005) showed that exogenous H_2O_2 induced tolerance to high temperature and freezing in potato plants. Wu et al. (1995 and 1997) observed that transgenic potato plants expressing a fungal gene encoding glucose oxidase, which generates H_2O_2 when glucose is oxidized, exhibited strong resistance to *Erwinia carotovora subsp carotovora*, and to *Phytophthora infestans*. This resistance to soft rot and to potato late blight was apparently mediated by elevated levels of H_2O_2 . The results of the present study demonstrated that plants mechanical infected with potato virus Y (PVY) suffered significantly harmful effects on pigment contents and on plant weight. These effects were reduced by injected the plants with *Thymus serpyllum* and *Lavandula officinalis* oil and spraying with H_2O_2 or AA. Concerning the changes in the leaves pigment contents, foliar mosaic (alternativ pale green and dark green areas) represents a common symptom of primary infection with potato virus Y (PVY). Our results show that the presence of potato virus Y (PVY) in tobacco plants significantly reduced the content of chlorophyll a, chlorophyll b. *Thymus serpyllum* and *Lavandula officinalis* oil injections and H_2O_2 or AA treatments of mechanical infected plants with potato virus Y (PVY) significantly increased the levels of chlorophylls compared with positive control plants, while similarly treated uninfected plants sprayed did not show significant differences in these pigments.

Under greenhouse conditions, 90 days after emergence, the inoculated and treated plants produced a higher biomass than the untreated positive controls. Reduced weight of plants is a characteristic response to stress in tobacco. The virus also cause an array of symptoms suggestive of disturbances in the normal balance of plant hormones such as cytokinins and auxins (Dermastia, 1995). It has been suggested that a physiological balance of antioxidant components is necessary in order to obtain protection to generalized stress; however, antioxidants are not always accessible to some of the sites where they are most needed in times of stress (Foyer et al., 1994). Our results agree with this statement since the *Thymus serpyllum* and *Lavandula officinalis* oil injections and AA/ H_2O_2 treatments induced

significant anti-stress effects in the tubers from positive plants.

This research presents a novel potential approach for overcoming the most common damage (for *Solanaceae* Family) of potato virus Y (PVY) infected material, using natural compounds that offer the possibility of reduction of biocide usage.

Conclusions

The results of the present study demonstrated that tobacco plants mechanical infected with potato virus Y (PVY) suffered significantly harmful effects on pigment contents and on fresh weight. These effects were reduced by injected the plants with *Thymus serpyllum* and *Lavandula officinalis* oil and spraying with H_2O_2 or AA. The treatments of infected plants with potato virus Y significantly increased the levels of chlorophylls a and b compared with positive control plants, while similarly treated uninfected plants did not show significant differences in these pigments.

Concerning the antiviral effect of the *Thymus serpyllum* and *Lavandula officinalis* oils, the injected tobacco plants presented after PVY mechanical inoculation absorbances values at 405nm significantly lower than the untreated and inoculated controls.

The elucidation of the precise role played by *Thymus serpyllum* and *Lavandula officinalis* oil treatments in addition with H_2O_2 , AA on potato virus Y infected and healthy tobacco plants awaits further investigation.

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- Abbreviations:** AA ascorbic acid; ROS reactive oxygen species; TS *Thymus serpyllum* ; LO *Lavandula officinalis*; PVY potato virus Y; OD optic density; SD standard deviation; dil-dilution

DINAMIC MODELATION OF THE TECHNICAL SYSTEM TRACTOR – POTATO HARVESTING MACHINE

I. CĂPĂÎNĂ* Gh. BRĂTUCU** FI. LOGHIN***

Abstract: *The works of potatoes harvesting are big consumers of power, reason for which is preferred their execution with special equipments with big power tractors. The concrete condition from the Romanian agriculture compel it on his farmers to use at such works tractors on wheels of middling power, witch will be intensely used. In the paper it s presented the dynamic and the mathematic model of the system tractor with equipment for potatoes harvesting.*

Keywords: *tractor, potato, working process, dynamic model.*

1. Introduction

In the case of using the agricultural tractors to works potatoes harvesting, can appear the solicitation in these transmissions which outruns the values of the assurance coefficients established by the builders for some pieces and parts. For this reason, to the formation of the working systems of this type is had to know good the level of capability for different elements, as well as of maxims solicitations whereat can be exposed to some working regimes.

For the tractor transmission is can be admitted as the regime of operation most difficult is the one of clutching or coupling of active organs of the working equipments, when the shocks can exceed the specific coefficients assurance for different parts. [1]

A modern method for investigate the dynamic solicitations of the system tractor-potato harvesting machine, in non-stationary operation regimes; it's represented by the modelation process. In this case it is necessary to achieve a dynamic model of the system and then a mathematical one, in order to solve we need to appealed to the digital values obtained from the experimental researches.

2. The Realization of the Dynamic Model of the Tractor-Potatoes Harvesting Machine

The solicitations which operate in the tractor transmission at work with the potatoes harvesting machine is complex and diverse, and contain their simultaneous in a system is a difficult problem. Therefore it is necessary some hypotheses and simplifications, strength the real

phenomenon specific for the transitory working regime can be replaced by a dynamic equivalent system, operation known as the dynamic *modelation*.

The theoretical research on the dynamic equivalent model becomes very commode, because all the elements of real system (the moments of inertias masses, the elastic constants and of amortization of the elastic components, the perturbation factors etc.) can be transmitted to the part witch the solicitation mast by known. Through the interpretation of the results of the torsion vibration of the model and considering the hypotheses and the simplifications made to the modelation it can be obtained information considering the dynamic real solicitations that appear in the working process.[2]

The process of modelation implies a good cognition of the perturbation factors, but a big care for the effusion and the application of the simplifying hypotheses. In this case it is necessary to appreciate correctly which masses, elastic elements and amortizations are envisaged or are neglect, as well as which among the variations lows of the perturbation factors are important in the studied process. For instance, although to modelation the cranked axels of the system are considered without mass, in practice there mass is disposed on there length, what does as the torsion vibration of dynamic model not to be identically with the one of the real system. For the practical calculus this discrepancy is unimportant.

Taking into consideration that the dynamic solicitations from the tractors transmission to the work with potatoes harvesting machines, have the most big values to the starting from place and the

takeoff, therefore to clutching, is can achieve a transmission of all the elements from the dynamic model to the clutch.

If we consider the technical system from the Figure 1, made by a tractor and a potatoes harvesting machine whereat the power engine

can be used as much for traction (Figure 1), and for the entrainment of the active organs through the plug of power, is can represent and this transmission (Figure 2), where are presented the elements about are shall don the analyses of solicitations.

Fig.1. Technically system tractor-potatoes harvesting machine

Fig. 2. The cinematically structure of the tractor transmission

Fig. 3. Dynamical model of the technically system tractor-potatoes harvesting machine

In the Figure 3 is presented a dynamic model of the tractor – potatoes harvesting machine system. To this elaboration the model is considered as the minimum number of masses of the system must envisaged at the modelation of the non-steady working process is 5, that is just as made in the Figure 3.

In this the figure are adopted the following notations:

- J_i - the moments of inertias transmitted to the clutches for the next masses from the real system: J_1 - mobile masses of the engine, of the flywheel and the conductress part of the clutch, value periodic variable, which in calculus is shall be considered constant; J_2 - the mass of the drive disk of the clutch; J_3 - the organs of the transmission funded out on the move of rotation; J_4 - mass of the rear wheels (with traction) of the 4x2 tractor; J_5 - total mass of the system tractor – potatoes harvesting machine fund out on the

translational move; J_6 - the masses of potatoes harvesting machine moved trough the power take off.

- $k_{i,i+1}$ - the elastic torsion constants transmitted to the clutch, characterizes the elastic connections among masses J_i and J_{i+1} ;
- $c_{i,i+1}$ - the elastic constants of amortization transmitted to the clutch proper of elastic connections among masses J_i and J_{i+1} ;
- A - the main clutch considered as a coupling with friction;
- K_1 - the mechanic coupling with friction which symbolizes the connection of the driving wheels with the soil;
- $\varphi_i, \dot{\varphi}_i$ and $\ddot{\varphi}_i$ - the angular movements, the angular speeds and the angular accelerations transmitted to the clutches of the masses J_i and J_{i+1} ;
- M_m - the torsion moment developed from the engine and applied to mass J_1 ;

- M_a - the friction moment from the main clutch;
- M_ϕ - the torsion moment transmitted from the driving wheels through adherence with the soil, transmitted to the clutch;
- M_r - the resistant torque(to the movement of the system tractor –potatoes harvesting machine), transmitted to the clutch;
- M_p - the resistant torque transmitted through the power take off;
- δ - the skid of the driving wheels of the tractor.[3]

In the skid process of the clutch the conducting part shall have the same motion with the mass J_1 , and the part drive is characterized by the angular movement φ_2 and the angular speed $\dot{\varphi}_2$. Alike, in the skid process of the driving wheels with the soil, these surface funded out in contact with the road shall have the angular movement φ'_5 and the angular speed $\dot{\varphi}'_5$, and the body tractor shall be characterized through the same values φ_5 and $\dot{\varphi}_5$.

Are considered concentrating masses, those parts and organs founded on the rotation

movement, of which the dimension of axis of rotation doesn't outruns 1...2 either their diameter. If the dimensions of the parts are not in the established limits, these masses must be distributed in some concentrating masses. If two or many masses are bonded through very rigid elements (the elastic constant is big), they can be concentrate in a single masses. The translational masses of the system are considered intent in the mass centers of tractor and potatoes harvesting machine.

3. The Mathematic Model of the Tractor-Potatoes harvesting machine System.

For the dynamic model from figure 2 is considered correct from the mathematical modelation the principle of D'alembert(the kyneto-statical method), as per whom, at one time, the outside forces, the connection forces and inertial forces which influences the system are in balance. [4]

The mathematical proper model of dynamic model from the Figure 3 (system tractor 4x2 – potatoes harvesting machine) has the next form:

- for $0 < \dot{\varphi}_1 < \dot{\varphi}_2$:

$$J_1 \cdot \ddot{\varphi}_1 + M_a + c_{16}(\varphi_1 - \varphi_6) + k_{16}(\dot{\varphi}_1 - \dot{\varphi}_6) = M_m;$$

$$M_a = \begin{cases} \frac{M_n \cdot \beta_d}{t_{1a}} & \text{for } 0 < t \leq t_1; \\ M_n \cdot \beta_s & \text{for } t > t_1. \end{cases}$$

$$M_m = \begin{cases} M_n \left(1 - \frac{\dot{\varphi}_1 - \dot{\varphi}_{nd}}{\dot{\varphi}_g - \dot{\varphi}_{nd}} \right) & \text{for } \dot{\varphi}_n \leq \dot{\varphi}_1 < \dot{\varphi}_g; \\ M_n + (M_{\max} - M_n) \frac{\dot{\varphi}_{nd} - \dot{\varphi}_1}{\dot{\varphi}_{nd} - \dot{\varphi}_{M \max d}} & \text{for } \dot{\varphi}_{M \max d} \leq \dot{\varphi}_1 < \dot{\varphi}_{nd}. \end{cases}$$

$$J_2 \cdot \ddot{\varphi}_2 + c_{23}(\varphi_2 - \varphi_3) + k_{23}(\dot{\varphi}_2 - \dot{\varphi}_3) = M_a;$$

$$c_{23}(\varphi_2 - \varphi_3) + k_{23}(\dot{\varphi}_2 - \dot{\varphi}_3) = A1;$$

$$J_3 \ddot{\varphi}_3 - c_{23}(\varphi_2 - \varphi_3) - k_{23}(\dot{\varphi}_2 - \dot{\varphi}_3) + c_{34}(\varphi_3 - \varphi_4) + k_{34}(\dot{\varphi}_3 - \dot{\varphi}_4) = 0;$$

$$c_{34}(\varphi_3 - \varphi_4) + k_{34}(\dot{\varphi}_3 - \dot{\varphi}_4) = A2;$$

$$J_4 \ddot{\varphi}_4 - c_{34}(\varphi_3 - \varphi_4) - k_{34}(\dot{\varphi}_3 - \dot{\varphi}_4) + c_{45}(\varphi_4 - \varphi'_5) + k_{45}(\dot{\varphi}_4 - \dot{\varphi}'_5) = 0;$$

$$c_{45}(\varphi_4 - \varphi'_5) + k_{45}(\dot{\varphi}_4 - \dot{\varphi}'_5) = M_K;$$

$$\varphi'_5 = \frac{\varphi_5}{\eta_\delta};$$

$$\dot{\varphi}'_5 = \frac{\dot{\varphi}_5}{\eta_\delta};$$

(1)

$$\eta_{\delta} = 1 - \frac{C \cdot K - D \cdot K^2}{E - K};$$

$$K = M_a \frac{i_{tr}}{Y_m \cdot r_m};$$

$$J_5 \cdot \ddot{\varphi}_5 = M_a - M_r;$$

$$J_6 \cdot \ddot{\varphi}_6 - c_{16}(\varphi_1 - \varphi_6) - k_{16}(\dot{\varphi}_1 - \dot{\varphi}_6) = -M_p;$$

$$M_p = M_{p0} \cdot \sin \dot{\varphi}_6 \cdot t;$$

$$M_r = M_{r0} \cdot \sin \dot{\varphi}_5 \cdot t;$$

• for $\dot{\varphi}_1 = \dot{\varphi}_2$:

$$(J_1 + J_2) \cdot \ddot{\varphi}_1 + c_{23}(\varphi_2 - \varphi_3) + k_{23}(\dot{\varphi}_2 - \dot{\varphi}_3) + c_{16}(\varphi_1 - \varphi_6) + k_{16}(\dot{\varphi}_1 - \dot{\varphi}_6) = M_a;$$

$$\dot{\varphi}_1 = \dot{\varphi}_2;$$

$$M_m = M_a;$$

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The other equations remain identically as in the case (1).

In the systems of equations (1) and (2) the other symbols have the next significations:

- φ_{nd} , φ_g and φ_{Mmaxd} - the angular movements of the nominal moment, of the free running and the maximum moment of the engine to dynamic solicitations;
- $A1$ - the torque transmitted to the clutch;
- $A2$ - the torque transmitted through adherence of the driving wheels with the soil;
- η_{δ} - the skid efficaciousness of the driving wheels on soils;
- C , D , E , K - coefficients which characterized the adherences of the driving wheels with the soil;
- Y_m - the vertical forces of reaction on the driving wheel;
- r_m - the driving wheel radius;
- M_{p0} - the resistance average moment at movement of the power take off.

If in the equation systems (1) and (2) are entered the specific values of the elements components are obtained the values of solicitations from clutches.

Through the transition at another part of all values from the equation systems (1) and (2) it can be obtain the values solicitations in that part.

The mathematical suggested model in any situation must be validated through rigorous experimental investigations, because same

simplifications of the variation of the parameters can drive to sensitive differences between the theoretical output and the experimental output. In the mathematical model presented it can enter the characteristic elements of any type of tractor 4x2 and of any type of potatoes harvesting machine, for which it can feigned differently work conditions, which produced the solicitations which can be used by the designers to a correct parts building.

4. Conclusions

- Through dynamically and mathematically correct modelations can by simulated the solicitations which can appear in the tractors transmissions on wheels when these work with equipments for potatoes harvesting.
- The accuracy of the simulation depends on the equations exactness of the mathematical model and on the degree of knowledge of parameters value which step in the systems of equations. The excessive simplification of the variation of this perturbation factors can distort the results.
- In the case of modeling the system tractor – potatoes harvesting machine, through the plug of power, as much the dynamic and the

mathematical model shall be completed with specified masses and equations.

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RESEARCH REGARDING THE INFLUENCE OF PARTICLE SIZE AND TEMPERATURE ON THE CYCLONE EFFICIENCY

M. MARINUC*

Abstract: *The separation processes are crucial to industry like chemical, petrochemical, mining, pharmaceutical and agro-alimentary processing. Cyclones are the most widely used separator devices which are based on the particle centrifugal force created by vortex in the cyclone. The paper describes how temperature and particle size influences the separation efficiency in the static devices type cyclones.*

Keywords: *cyclones, efficiency, particle dimensions, temperature.*

1. Introduction

The separation processes are crucial to industry like chemical, petrochemical, mining, pharmaceutical and agro-alimentary processing. Generally, it is a physical separation of two phases (Gas/Liquid, Gas/Solid, Liquid/Solid), i.e. a continuous phase (carrying phase), and a dispersed phase (particles). Cyclones are the most widely used separator devices which are based on the particle centrifugal force created by vortex in the cyclone. (1) Their simple design, low capital cost and nearly maintenance-free operation make them ideal for use as pre-cleaners for more expensive final control devices such as bag houses or electrostatic precipitators.

There are three primary reasons for separating gases from solids in solids processing: to minimize emissions for environmental purposes, to protect other processing equipment (turbines, etc.) from particle-laden streams, and to stop unwanted gas solids reactions from occurring. The primary separator in most fluidized bed processes is a cyclone. The efficiency of separation achieved by the cyclone depends upon the nature of the process. If the process stream is dry and the particles are relatively large and free flowing, collection is relatively easy. If is not, or there is special chemistry or extreme temperature involved, particulate collection can be challenging. (2)

The basis for many of the empirical separation efficiency models is the condition in which a particle of a particular size and density would orbit indefinitely around the axis of the cyclone. (3)

2. Collection efficiency of cyclones

The principle of separation in a cyclone is to increase the effect of sedimentation by centrifugal force, which is made by introducing tangential suspension in a device. The efficiency of separation cyclones is much higher than dusting rooms because in a centrifugal force field, the effect of separation is maximized.

In the case of cyclones, the effect of centrifugal force manifests itself differently from particles and gas. Due to centrifugal force the solid particles are thrown to the wall where they lose energy and fall moving under the action of gravity at the bottom of the device where it is discharged (particle mass > gas mass). So, gas is moving downward spiral, solid particles being driven to the top of the gas and then gas (air) is discharged through the central tube of the cyclone due to the circulation effect. (4)

Cyclone efficiency characterizes its ability to retain from fluid environment the solid particles of a certain minimum size required. At the same cyclone, changing the particle density and fluid viscosity, changes its efficiency. To retain the minimum of particles diameter required is necessary to align the input speed of the fluid in the cyclone with product characteristics (density of the medium, particle density, and viscosity) and constructive parameters of the cyclone.

Efficiency of solids separation in a cyclone has typical value of 70-80%, but if the fluid is loaded with large amounts of solids, separation

* Dept. of Food Engineering, Transilvania University of Braşov, Romania, e-mail: mimy_85@yahoo.com

efficiency exceeds 99%. Separation in cyclones is favorable with large particles that would normally be entirely separate, the fluid, in the output will contain only particles smaller than the critical diameter. But, the swirling

formed inside the cyclone influence the process of separation. (5)

Fig. 1. Diagram of grade efficiency curve characteristics from Stairmand (1951)

Stairmand (1951) described the collection efficiency curve which indicates the efficiency of the cyclone for separating particles of given density over a range of sizes. This curve is also known as the grade efficiency curve. The x-axis plots particle size, usually in units of microns. The y-axis plots the collection or separation efficiency either as a fraction or as a percent. One point on the grade efficiency curve which is typically identified is the cut size. The cut size is defined as the particle size at which the separation efficiency is 50%. The cut size is identified in figure 1.

Researchers over the years have produced a number of predictive models that use empirical information related to the geometry and operating conditions of specific cyclone designs and are intended to estimate cyclone collection efficiency. Leith (1984) summarized a number of these models. His list included models by Stairmand (1951), Barth (1956), Lapple (1951) and Leith and Licht (1972). Ogawa (1984) also

reviewed a number of predictive models including Lapple and Shepherd (1940), Barth

(1956) and Stairmand (1951). He also presented his own theoretical predictions. (6)

3. Work steps

For theoretical research regarding the influence of particle size dimensions on the separation efficiency were used the cyclone dimensions resulting from the calculation and using AutoCAD. For dimensional calculating it was chosen an input speed of impure gas in the inlet pipe 15 m/s and a volume flow 400 m³/s. With this data we determined the size of the cyclone parts according to geometric similarity reports of a cyclone type chosen. Thus, parts of the cyclone size used in theoretical research are shown in figure 2.

To calculate cyclone efficiency have used the following formula:

$$\eta = 1 - \exp \left[-2 \left(C \Psi \right)^{\frac{1}{2m+2}} \right] \cdot 100 [\%] \quad (1)$$

where:

η - efficiency of the cyclone;

C - parameter that depends on the size of the cyclone:

$$C = \frac{8K_c}{K_a K_b}; \quad C = 2664,43; \quad (2)$$

$$K_a + K_b = a \cdot b = 0,0074; \quad (3)$$

K_c - constant of the basis time what is supporting the particles within the vortex system:

$$K_c = \frac{V_s + V_{el}}{D^3}; \quad K_c = 2,47792; \quad (4)$$

$$V_s - \text{Upper volume: } V_s = \frac{\pi D^2}{4} h, [m^3];$$

$$V_s = 0,02617 m^3; \quad (5)$$

V_{el} - Volume actually heading back to the lower vortex in the cyclone:

$$V_{el} = \frac{\pi \cdot D^2}{4} (h - s) + \frac{\pi \cdot D^2}{4} \left(\frac{\ln \frac{s+h}{3}}{3} \left(1 + \frac{d}{D} + \frac{d^2}{D^2} \right) \right) \frac{\pi \cdot D_e^2 \cdot \ln}{4}, [m^3]; \quad V_{el} = 0,01916 m^3; \quad (6)$$

\ln – natural length of cyclone:

$$\ln = 2.3 D_e \left(\frac{D^2}{a \cdot b} \right)^{\frac{1}{8}}, [m];$$

$$\ln = 0,516 m; \quad (7)$$

$$d = D - (D - D_B) \left(\frac{s + \ln - h}{H - h} \right), [m];$$

$$d = 0,23332 m. \quad (8)$$

Ψ - Inertial impact parameter which depends on the nature of gas-solid:

$$\Psi = \frac{\rho_s \cdot d_p^2 \cdot v_{t2}}{18 \mu \cdot D} (m + 1); \quad (9)$$

μ - Gas mixture viscosity;

$$\mu = (37.4 + 0.506 \cdot T) \cdot 10^{-5};$$

$$T = 293 [K]; \quad (10)$$

m - Alexander's number, which is consistent with the size and temperature gas cyclone:

$$m = 0,5;$$

d_p - Dimensions of dust particles, $d_p = [1 \div 75] [\mu m];$

ρ_s - Solid particle density: $\rho_s = 2525 [kg/m^3];$

v_{t2} - Velocity of the gas to the entry into the supply: $v_{t2} = 15 m/s;$

The above results were obtained after the introduction of known parameters and calculation formulas in Microsoft Office Excel 2003 and were listed in table 1.

4. Results and discussions

particle dust size. It was used six different diameters of solid particles: $5 \cdot 10^{-6}$; $10 \cdot 10^{-6}$; $15 \cdot 10^{-6}$; $20 \cdot 10^{-6}$; $25 \cdot 10^{-6}$ and $30 \cdot 10^{-6}$, and one constant temperature $T= 293$ K. (figure 3).

In the case of effect temperature over the separation efficiency in cyclone with tangential

To emphasize the separation theoretical efficiency corresponding graphs were drawn. The first graphic it was drawn according to entry, it were used the same dimensions of solid particle dust which were mentioned above, temperature taking the following values: $T= 293$ K; $T= 303$ K; $T= 313$ K; $T= 323$ K; $T=333$ K; and $T=343$ K. (figure 4).

Table 1.

Separation efficiency values

m	v [m/s]	ρ [kg/m ³]	d [m]	C	D [m]	m	Y	B	expB	η [%]
0,5	15	1,3	0,000005	2647	0,244	0,00185	0,000009	-0,57547	0,562	43,756
0,5	15	1,3	0,00001	2647	0,244	0,00185	0,000036	-0,91351	0,401	59,888
0,5	15	1,3	0,000015	2647	0,244	0,00185	0,000081	-1,19703	0,302	69,791
0,5	15	1,3	0,00002	2647	0,244	0,00185	0,000144	-1,4501	0,235	76,545
0,5	15	1,3	0,000025	2647	0,244	0,00185	0,000225	-1,68269	0,186	81,413
0,5	15	1,3	0,00003	2647	0,244	0,00185	0,000324	-1,90017	0,150	85,046

which will be separated is a very important factor in choosing the cyclone type.

Fig. 3. Diameter effect over separation efficiency

Fig. 4. Temperature effect over separation efficiency

5. Conclusions

The efficiency of the separation process increases with particle size solids involved in the separation operation, the size of solid particles

The temperature, at which the separation is made, also influences the efficiency of separation process, as high temperature the separation process has a higher performance.

It is very important that in choosing the separation device to take into account the working parameters (temperature, pressure etc.), mixture characteristics, solid particle characteristics (viscosity, density, dimensions etc.)

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RESEARCH ON THE KINEMATICS OF FLOW REGIME ON FLUID MIXING

Mihaela Ionela LUCHIAN*

Abstract: *Mixing theory is important for its relevance in understanding some of the most fundamental problems involving viscoelastic fluid (bread dough) flows, and for its practical impact in connection with bakery industry and other food industries. The flow regime of bread dough is important in understanding the mixing mechanism.*

Flow in classical and quantum fluid mechanics can be classified into one of two broad categories or regimes: laminar and turbulent flows. The food industry regularly deals with viscous fluids, which necessitate mixing in the laminar flow regime, where effective mixing may prove challenging. This paper discusses the role of turbulent and laminar flow of visco-elastic fluid mixing.

Keywords: *mixing, fluid, flow, laminar, turbulent*

1. Introduction

Mixing is a fundamental unit operation in food process industries. Mixing increases the homogeneity of a system by reducing non-uniformity or gradients in composition, properties or temperature. Besides the primary objective of homogeneity, secondary objectives of mixing include control of heat and mass transfer rates, reactions and structural changes. [3]. In bakery industry, additional mixing challenges include sanitary design, complex rheology, desire for continuous processing and the effects of mixing on final product texture and sensory profiles.

Mixing is frequently employed to develop the desired product characteristics such as texture rather than simply ensure product homogeneity. If mixing fails to achieve the required product yield, quality, and organoleptic or functional attributes, production costs may increase significantly.

Mixing theory has attracted the interest of engineers for its relevance in understanding some of the most fundamental problems involving fluid flows, and for its practical impact in connection with the food processing industries. [1]

Turbulence plays a central role in many mixing processes and is commonly induced by the process industries in mixers to facilitate effective mixing.

However, the food industry (even the bakery industry) regularly deals with viscous fluids,

which necessitate mixing in the laminar flow regime, where effective mixing may prove challenging.

2. Fluid mixing

The modern approach to the study of mixing in laminar fluid flows applies dynamical systems theory and concepts to the Lagrangian description of fluid flow. The Lagrangian description uses Cartesian coordinates that move with a particle.

When we speak of a fluid particle, we mean an element of fluid of negligible dimensions. The equations of fluid motion are obtained by applying the principles of mechanics to a fluid particle. In the case of an incompressible viscous (Newtonian) fluid of uniform density, considering the Navier–Stokes equations for an incompressible fluid, the following equations are obtained: [8]; [15].

$$\frac{\partial u}{\partial t} + \omega \cdot u + \frac{1}{2} \nabla u^2 = -\nabla \left(\frac{p}{\rho} \right) + \nu \nabla^2 u \quad (1)$$

$$\nabla \cdot u = 0,$$

where, $\omega = \nabla \cdot u$ is the vorticity, $\omega \cdot u$ is the Lamb vector, p is the pressure, ρ is the density and $\nabla^2 u$ is the dissipation field. Solving these Navier–Stokes equations, we obtain the velocity field $u(x, t)$. The dynamical systems setting for

* Dept. of Food Product Engineering, Transylvania University of Brasov, Romania, e-mail: m_luchian@yahoo.com

the study of the transport and mixing of a fluid particle is the study of the trajectories of:

$$\dot{x} = u(x, t) \quad (2)$$

where each initial condition corresponds to a different fluid particle. A trajectory is the path the fluid particle takes through the fluid, and the phase space is physical space. [8]; [15].

To investigate the mixing in a fully three-dimensional laminar flow, it is difficult to obtain $u(x, t)$ because the majority of studies have been restricted to time-dependent forcing of 2D velocity fields and 3D flows based on qualitative or kinematic models which mimic a velocity field but do not satisfy equations (1). [5]; [9].

Only by studying the kinematics of velocity fields satisfying the Navier–Stokes equations can understanding be achieved of how inertia and viscosity influence the mixing properties throughout the fluid, a question of both fundamental and practical interest.

The Navier–Stokes equations for a Newtonian fluid are simply equations for the velocity *vector* field, whereas the rheological equations for a viscoelastic fluid (as bread dough) involve a nonlinear constitutive equation for the stress *tensor*. Any calculation is therefore much harder for visco-elastic flow, and even conceptually simple approximation schemes often lead to cumbersome expressions with many terms. [2]; [4]

3. Kinematics of fluid flow

Fluid flow can be expressed by either one of two ways: Lagrangian or Eulerian approaches. To express fluid velocity with the Eulerian approach, a point in a flow field is selected using the Cartesian coordinate system (x, y, z) , and observed changes in properties such as velocity, pressure and/or temperature as the fluid passes through this particular point are measured.

However, in the steady state condition, the flow properties are no longer a function of time. The Eulerian viewpoint is commonly used, and it is the preferred method in the study of fluid mechanics. In this case, velocity depends upon the point in space and time. In the Lagrangian viewpoint, an individual fluid particle is considered for all time. The Lagrangian description of fluid mechanics is based on an observer following the trajectories of fluid particles, which are moving mathematical fluid

points of infinitesimal size but large compared to molecular dimensions as required by continuum assumptions. [11]

In this approach, as the fluid particle travels about the flow field, the changes in flow properties such as velocity is obtained by differentiating the position vector $[r(t)]$ with respect to time:

$$r(t) = xi + yj + zk$$

$$V(t) = \frac{dx}{dt}i + \frac{dy}{dt}j + \frac{dz}{dt}k \quad (3)$$

$$V(t) = ui + vj + wk$$

where i, j, k are unit vectors in x, y, z directions and u, v, w are the respective component velocities.

It is not practical to keep track of the positions of all particles in a flow field; consequently, the Eulerian approach is often preferred over the Lagrangian approach. However, both the approaches can be used in the study of fluid mechanics. A Lagrangian approach following the motion of infinitesimal material fluid elements (which by definition move with the local instantaneous flow) is conceptually natural and practically useful for describing turbulent transport. [11]

The kinematic approach has contributed to a better understanding of existing mixing devices as well as to the rational design of new ones. [12]; [13]

Motion of individual particles in a fluid can be either regular, which is integrable (terminology used for regular flow), or chaotic. A laminar flow field is one in which velocity, pressure and other flow parameters do not vary irregularly with time.

A chaotic flow field is one in which the path and final position of a particle placed within the field are extremely sensitive to their initial position.

Before discussing mixing in various flow regimes, it is important to quantify the flow regime.

Flow in classical and quantum fluid mechanics can be classified into one of two broad categories or regimes, namely, laminar and turbulent flows.

The flow regime, whether laminar or turbulent, is important in understanding the mixing mechanism.

Fig.1. Types of fluid flow

Laminar flow exists over a very low range of velocities, whereas turbulent flow occurs at higher velocities. When viscous forces predominate, the flow is laminar. Conversely, in turbulent flow, inertial forces dominate and the fluid forms eddies with widely different length and time scales. However, such predictions are valid only for constant flow and become more difficult where flow is pulsatile or radial.

The situation is further complicated if the contained fluid is non-Newtonian. [8] In general, the pattern of the flow varies with the velocity, the physical properties of the fluid and the geometry of the surface.

In the majority of moderate and high-speed flow problems, some form of random variation of flow variables exists.

The laminar treatment is generally not applicable when such variations occur. Turbulent flow is defined as a flow with random variation of various flow quantities such as velocity, pressure and density. Turbulence is a property of a flow, not that of a fluid. [14]

In turbulent flow, the inertia stresses dominate over the viscous stresses, leading to small-scale chaotic behaviour in the fluid motion.

Turbulent flow is generally dominated by recirculation, swirling of a fluid or apparent randomness. Recirculation or randomness does not necessarily indicate turbulent flow, and it may also be present in laminar flow.

Flows of visco-elastic fluids (such as bread dough) are characterised by the Weissenberg number (Wb) which measures the importance of relaxation, elasticity and anisotropy effects due to the viscoelasticity.

The Reynolds number (Re) and Weissenberg number (Wb) behave in a similar fashion. However, transformation towards turbulent flow for either case largely depends upon flow geometry. [7]

4. Shear flow

Turbulence is intrinsically time dependent, with continual reorientation of the fluid particle. Mixing in the laminar flow regime depends on molecular diffusion.

Shear flows occur when force is applied parallel to a face of a fluid element (shear stress, σ) and results in a shear deformation where there is an angular displacement of parallel surfaces in the fluid element (shear strain, γ). The rate at which the shear deformation occurs is the shear rate ($\dot{\gamma}$). Shear flow is the dominate flow type found in most mixers.

The typical rheological behaviours of fluid foods under steady shear conditions are depicted in the rheogram in Figure 2.

Fig.2. Flow curves for typical time-independent fluids. 1—viscoplastic fluid, 2—Bingham fluid, 3—pseudoplastic fluid, 4—Newtonian fluid and 5—dilatant fluid. [8]

The most basic behaviour is the case in which the shear stress is proportional to the shear rate as seen in curve 4, where the slope is the Newtonian viscosity (μ) as was originally defined by Newton's viscosity law. Curves 3 and 5 describe shear thinning (or pseudoplastic) and shear thickening (or dilatant) behaviours, respectively, and are both described by the power law model. Curves 1 and 2 describe fluids that have a dynamic yield stress (σ_y) that must be overcome before fluid flow commences.

At stress levels greater than the yield stress, Bingham fluids (curve 2) exhibit shear stress that is proportional to shear rate with the slope described as the plastic viscosity (μ_{pl}), whereas fluids exhibiting continued shear thinning behaviour are described as viscoplastic (curve 1).

This range of behaviours can be generally described using the Herschel–Bulkley model: [8]

$$\sigma = \sigma_y + K \cdot \dot{\gamma}^n \quad (4)$$

where K is the consistency coefficient and n is the flow behaviour index. It directly describes the behaviour seen in curve 1 of Figure 1 as well as that in curve 2 when $n = 1$ to give the Bingham model, where $K = \mu_{pl}$. When the yield stress is zero ($\sigma_y = 0$), equation (4) takes the form of the power law model with the pseudoplastic behaviour of curve 3 modelled when $n < 1$ and dilatant behaviour of curve 5 modelled when $n > 1$. In the case where both $\sigma_y = 0$ and $n = 1$, equation (1) reduces to the Newtonian case of curve 4 where K becomes the Newtonian viscosity (μ).

Conclusions

The present paper offers an overview for understanding some of the most fundamental problems involving fluid flows. Turbulence plays a central role in the mixing process and is commonly induced by the process industries in mixers to facilitate effective mixing.

It is important to study the kinematics of velocity fields for understanding how inertia and viscosity influence the mixing properties throughout the fluid.

The Navier–Stokes equations for a Newtonian fluid are simply equations for the velocity *vector* field, whereas the rheological equations for a visco-elastic fluid involve a nonlinear constitutive equation for the stress *tensor*, and the calculation is much harder for visco-elastic flow, and even conceptually simple approximation schemes often lead to cumbersome expressions with many terms.

In mixing process is important to quantify the flow regime, which can be classified into one of two broad categories or regimes, namely, laminar and turbulent flows.

Laminar flow exists over a very low range of velocities, whereas turbulent flow occurs at higher velocities. When viscous forces predominate, the flow is laminar. In turbulent flow, inertial forces dominate and the fluid forms eddies with widely different length and time scales

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OPPORTUNITIES FOR TOP RECOVERY OF FRUIT AND VEGETABLES BY CONSERVATION BY DRYING IN BRASOV AREA

A.L. MARIN*

GH. BRĂTUCU**

Abstract: *Specific climatic conditions of the area where Romania is located, with four seasons (winter, spring, summer and autumn) with a single agricultural crop a year, determined that, since ancient times, people worry about the preservation of fruits and vegetables they eat in the period between harvests, especially during the cold season. The fruits that can be dried are apples, pears, plums, apricots and grapes (seedless grain). They have food uses of the most diverse and attractive. By the vegetables, can be dried that cannot be keep, but which are often used in food, such as: the pods of green beans, peppers (bell, chili, Kapi, pepper), dill, garden thyme, mushrooms.*

Keywords: *conservation, vegetables, fruit, drying, food*

1. Introduction

Drying, which initially was made naturally in the sun, is undoubtedly the oldest method of preserving vegetables and fruits. Then drying technology has progressed through the use of heat produced by wood burning in proper kiln.

Today's technology is based on dehydration, which is an improved method of drying. Dehydrated fruits and vegetables, packaged properly, can be kept very long time without requiring cold storage. The main methods used today to conserve vegetables and fruits by removing water are:

- natural drying,
- controlled dehydration.

Drying should be defined as the natural process based on natural heat transfer, which ensures the water evaporation from product surface, which allows the removal of moisture of materials in the form found in nature, or displayed in the form of pastes, granules, wedges.

Dehydration should be defined as the artificially process, based on heat transfer controlled by humans, which is largely done by "vaporizing" water from the material to be dehydrated, which allows the removal of moisture in the form of materials exposed as pastes, granules, sheets, plates, diced, sliced or even in the form found in nature.

2. Material and method

Unlike most agricultural products, fruits lend themselves well to drying in the sun because they contain high levels of sugar and acids that allow exposure in the open air without any danger to food security. Some dried fruits in these conditions, the most common are plums, raisins, dates and figs, but you can dry in the sun a much wider range of fruit that you can use them in the winter or as food ingredients or eat them as that, to obtain quality nutrients. The best fruit will dry in the sun when temperature remain around 30 degrees Celsius or higher and there is good air movement, even in the form of light breeze. A single day will not be enough for proper drying and fruit should be placed in a location where they can be quickly taken inside in case of rain.

In areas with high humidity is not at all indicated to dry fruits by this method because usually requires the humidity to be lower than 60 percent. In addition, at night they must be brought indoors or covered to protect from the effects of rising damp. As a useful device for fruit drying in the sun is best to use the blocks of stone, concrete blocks or other useful support to be placed under the surface that will serve to dry the fruits. This should not be too thick but rather to show like a tighter mesh to allow good air circulation and underneath, accelerating the drying of fruits in the best conditions. In other situations, it can also turn to the vertical suspension of fruit, fruit is placed in the special bag or cloth or strung on string. Very helpful is to

* Dept. of Food Engineering, *Transilvania University of Braşov*, Romania, e-mail: deea_marin2007@yahoo.com

** Dept of Food Engineering, *Transilvania University of Braşov*, Romania, e-mail: gh.bratucu@unitbv.ro

place first a large sheet of aluminum on earth, followed by placing blocks of stone and then the fruit storage area. Aluminum sheet will reflect the heat from underneath the fruit, ensuring a high drying on all sides. The best drying surfaces are made of stainless steel, fiberglass and coated in Teflon or plastic dish. Textile sheets favor fruit contamination with various pathogen agents and are not recommended. So it is with aluminum or copper, which oxidizes too quickly to be used in such operations in open air. Dehydration and drying processes are based on reducing natural water content, which increases soluble concentration to levels that would stabilize the preservation of fruits and vegetables. Remove water from vegetables and fruit should be conducted so as hydrophilic colloids contained to maintain rehydration capacity. Drying is a natural process carried out in nature without human intervention. Dehydration is an artificial process, led and controlled by humans. Both processes have the same goal, namely the removal of a part or all of the moisture contained by the exposed material. By sun-drying or heat drying, vegetables and fruit weight is reduced by 5 to 10 times comparative the fresh state.

Drying and dehydrating fruits and vegetables is the process by which natural moisture content is reduced to a level that would prevent the activity of microorganisms, without destroying tissue, or to devalue food products. The drying process (which is a natural process) contributes:

- heat transfer from the heated air by sun to the material to be dried;
- evaporation from the surface of the material to be dried;
- training and acquisition of water vapor formed at the surface of the material to be dried;
- migration of water from inside to its surface.

At drying there are two agents:

- material to be dried, which receives on its surface a quantity of heat, which leads some of the moisture from the surface to turn into vapor;
- air, naturally heated by the sun, which becomes a "gas heat", which has dual role:
 - to bring the heat needed for drying;
 - to retrieve and remove from the system the formed vapors.

The process of dehydration (which is an artificial process, developed and managed by humans) contribute:

- heat transfer from artificially heated air by using a fuel or electric current to the material to be dehydrated;
- water vaporizing from the material to be dehydrated;
- building a forced air circulation artificially heated to ensure training of water vapor emanated from the material to be dried.

The two agents involved in dehydration are:

- material to be dehydrated, which receives a quantity of heat which raises its temperature throughout its mass, and provides forced vaporization, total or partial of the moisture contained;
- artificially heated air is a "gas heating", with double role:
 - to bring heat required for water vaporization from the material to be dehydrated;
 - to retrieve and remove from the system the formed vapors.

3. Results and discussions

During drying, especially for dehydrated fruits and vegetables, are produced following transformation of raw material:

- structural changes by wrinkle and the reduction of volume due to reduction of water content and tissue contraction;
- changes in color. Fruit or vegetable color degradation is a function of temperature, duration of removing water, heavy metals, reducing sugar content but also the result of oxidative processes that occur;
- transformation of aroma and flavor. If hot air dehydration products has been made by driving steam, which is why there is a certain loss of flavor. In the case of natural drying losses of aroma and flavor are determined by the process and relative humidity of the environment in which are exposed the raw materials.
- reducing the amount of food. During the drying process, depending on the applied thermal regime, sensitive transformations occur in the chemical composition of products, which affect their food value.

The process of dehydration causes certain changes in dehydrated fruits and vegetables compared with fresh ones, namely:

- reduce the volume and weight;
- increase the amount of energy;
- are easy to prepare;

• lost a part of some useful chemical compounds. By thermal treatments in general (heating, boiling, drying heat) is losing the original quality. Phenomena that occur to dehydration are:

- loss of water to carbon dioxide;
- protein degradation;
- loss of vitamins.

Instead, they retain the content of sugars and organic acids, and as a result of decreasing weight, transportation costs, handling, storage is reduced.

The main fruit used in traditional diet, which can be dried (Fig. 1) are:

- plum - (*Prunus domestica*);
- apple - (*Malus domestica*);
- pears - (*Pyrrhus sativa*);
- apricot - (*Armeniaca vulgaris*);
- grape - (*Vitis vinifera*)
- Plant native spices:
 - savory - (*Satureja hortensis*), (*Thymus vulgaris*), (*Thymus serpyllum*)
 - mint - (*Mentha silvestris*).
 - dill - (*Anethum graveolens*);
 - celery leaves - (*Allium cepa*)

Fig. 1. Fruit species suitable for conservation by drying
a – plums; b – apples; c – pears; d – grapes

The main vegetables that can be dried (Fig. 2) are:

- bean pods - (*Phaseolus vulgaris*);
- pepper (capsicum, chili, peppers Kapi, bell pepper) - (*Capsicum annuum*)
- mushrooms - (*Boletus edulis*)

- carrot - (*Daucus carota sativa*);
- parsnips - (*Pastinaca sativa hortensis*);
- parsley root - (*Petroselinum hortense*)
- celery root - (*Apium graveolens*);
- onion - (*Allium cepa*)
- potato - (*Solanum tuberosum*).

Fig. 2. Vegetables species suitable for conservation by drying

Dried fruits are considered "true miracles" to health. Prepared in summer or autumn, dried fruit, rich in vitamins, fiber, micronutrients, are preferably consumed in winter and spring, representing a correct solution for balanced nutrition in cold season. However, dried fruits should be eaten sparingly because of high sugar and calories content. Dried and dehydrated fruits have a beneficial effect on the human body.

The main physiological actions are as follows:

- moisturizing effect, provided by sugar and minerals contained.
- diuretic effect, provided by potassium, magnesium and sodium;
- effect of alkali salts in the body by converting organic acids contained in alkali carbonates;
- effect of mineralization, providing minerals the human body;
- laxative effect, because the fibers contained;
- tonic action by the vitamins.

4. Conclusions

- Drying is the natural process based on heat transfer who ensures the water evaporation from product surface, which allows the removal of moisture of materials in the form found in nature, or displayed in the form of pastes, granules, wedges.

- Dehydration should be defined as the artificially process, based on heat transfer controlled by humans, which is largely done by "vaporizing" water from the material to be dehydrated, which allows the removal of moisture in the form of materials exposed as pastes, granules, sheets, plates, diced, sliced or even in the form found in nature.

- Dehydration and drying processes are based on reducing natural water content, which increases soluble concentration to levels that would stabilize the preservation of fruits and

vegetables. Remove water from vegetables and fruit should be conducted so as hydrophilic colloids contained to maintain rehydration capacity. Drying is a natural process carried out in nature without human intervention. Dehydration is an artificial process, led and controlled by humans.

- The best fruit will dry in the sun when temperatures remain around 30 degrees Celsius or higher and there is good air movement, even in the form of light breeze. A single day will not be enough for proper drying and fruit should be placed in a location where they can be quickly taken inside in case of rain.

- The best drying surfaces are made of stainless steel, fiberglass and coated in Teflon or plastic dish. Textile sheets favor fruit contamination with various pathogen agents and are not recommended. So it is with aluminum or copper, which oxidizes too quickly to be used in such operations in open air.

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TEMPERATURE CONTROL SIMULATION IN WAREHOUSES FOR AGRO ALIMENTARY PRODUCTS

C. PĂUNESCU* GH. BRĂTUCU*

Abstract: *In this paper is conceived and verified a temperature control simulation in a warehouse for fruits and vegetables with taking into account the disruptive elements which influences its constant maintenance. Keeping a constant temperature inside the warehouse cells assures the increase of storage duration but also maintaining fruits and vegetables water, vitamins and mineral substance etc. valuable content. The simulation is made in the Simulink module of Matlab software, which permits to model and analyze dynamics systems.*

Keywords: *simulation, temperature control, warehouse*

1. Introduction

In specialized literature are presented the optimal fruits and vegetables storing temperature values for achieving a long storing period. A quality parameter which characterizes the storage is the products weight and valuable substances loss during storage[1],[5].

In most cases the weight loss is due to fruits and vegetables dehydration, because of temperature, humidity and atmospheric composition variation inside the warehouse. In table 1 is presented the water content for the most important fruits and vegetables cultivated in Romania at harvesting time[2].

Table 1

Fruits and vegetables water content

Species	Water %	Organ	Species	Water %	Organ
Cranberries	80...84	Fruits	Beetroot	84...88	Roots
Gooseberries	83...85	Fruits	Celery	82...85	Roots
Hazelnuts	6...10	Fruits	Cucumbers	90...96	Fruits
Apricots	79...88	Fruits	Cauliflower	87...92	Inflorescence
Strawberries	87...93	Fruits	Green Onions	82...88	Leaf
Currants	83...88	Fruits	Onion	80...87	Bulbs
Cherries	75...87	Fruits	Potatoes	75...80	Tubercles
Quince	77...87	Fruits	Pumpkins	80...90	Fruits
Apples	77...88	Fruits	Zucchini	92...95	Fruits
Pears	79...86	Fruits	Horseradish	71...75	Roots
Plums	72...87	Fruits	Carrot	85...89	Roots
Grape	75...83	Fruits	Parsley	85...90	Roots
Bob (beans)	89...93	Fruits	Tomatoes	93...96	Fruits
Okra	75...90	Fruits	Garlic	70...74	Bulbs
Radishes	85...94	Roots	White cabbage	88...92	Leaf
Spinach	87...92	Leaf	Scotch kale	88...90	Leaf

* Dept. of Food Products Engineering, Transilvania University of Braşov, Romania, e-mail:catalin.paunescu85@yahoo.com

The water is a basis constituent of fruits and vegetables cells and no chemical reaction can be produced in its absence. Due to the influence that it has in carrying metabolic processes and over fruits sensibly to trauma, fruits and vegetable water content is having serious repercussion over products storing capacity. So high water content fruits and vegetables are having a smaller storing period comparing with those which have reduced water content. Fruits and vegetables water content variation during storage is influenced, mostly, by temperature variation, fact which will be correlated in the researches done in this paper.[1],[2].

2. Material and method

The title must be as short possible. If necessary, a subtitle is provided. For a precise simulation representation of temperature control was used Simulink software. This is an environment for multi-domain simulation and for design based on a model for dynamic and embedded systems. It offers a interactive graphic environment and a personalized set of libraries which permits designing, simulating and testing of a wide variety of systems.

The add-on products extends Simulink software for multiple modeling domains and also it offers tools for designing, implementation and validation.

Simulink is integrated with Matlab, offering instant access to a wide variety of equipments which permits algorithm development, simulation analyses, making scripts for batch processing, modeling environment personalization, signals definition etc.[3]

The first step in making this simulation is the development of the mathematic model which describes the physic phenomenon inside the warehouse cells. Therefore the following notations are made: $W_i(t)$ is the heat flow generated by the compressor, which enter inside the cell; $W_{p1}(t)$ - the heat flow which exits through walls; $W_{p2}(t)$ - the heat flow which is produced by the stored fruits or vegetables.

The cell thermal equilibrium equation is:

$$W_i(t) - W_{p1}(t) + W_{p2}(t) - C_T \cdot \frac{d\theta(t)}{dt}, \quad (1)$$

where: C_T is the inside air thermal capacity; $\theta(t)$ – temperature.

Following the equation (1) is passed from time domain into Laplace domain, by applying Laplace transformation at null initial conditions. So it is obtained the equivalent equation (2)[3]:

$$R_T W_i(s) + \theta_g(s) + R_T W_{p2}(s) = \theta(s)(1 + R_T C_T) \quad (2)$$

where R_T is the walls thermal transfer.

To obtain the mathematical model of the conduced object is admitted that the used temperature transducer has a negligible time constant and is described by the equation:

$$y(t) = K_T \theta(t) \quad (3)$$

The execution element is of proportional type and is having a delay of I order and is characterized by:

$$T_1 \frac{d\theta_g}{dt} + \theta_g = K_1 u \quad (4)$$

The cooling compressor is approximated by a proportional element with delay:

$$H_p(s) = \frac{Y(s)}{U(s)} = \frac{K_1 K_2 K_T R_T}{(1+T_1(s))(1+T_2(s))} \quad (6)$$

For this transfer function numeric expression are picked: $K_T = 0,2V/^{\circ}K$, $R_T = 0,2121m^2K/W$, $K_1 K_2 = 5W/V$, $C_T = 80Ws/^{\circ}K$, $T_1 = 8s$. and is obtained:

$$H_p(s) = \frac{0,04}{(1+8s)(1+17s)} \quad (7)$$

$$W_i(t) = K_2 \theta_g \quad (5)$$

where: θ_g is the cooled air flow, in m^3/s ; K_2 – the compressor proportional factor; K_1 – the execution element proportional factor.

It is noted with $T_2 = R_T C_T$ as being the time constant associated with the warehouse thermal capacity.

In this case the conduced object can be described by the relation between the system entrance and exit in Laplace domain, or in other words between the command and the system exit in Laplace domain which is represented by the measured temperature so by the conduced object transfer function:

To adjust the described process it will be used a PID regulator and taking into account the perturbations (the heat flow which is lost through walls and the heat flow produced by the stored

fruits and vegetables) which action over the system. The PID parameters are accorded with Ziegler-Nichols algorithm and are obtained the following transfer function[3],[5]:

$$H_0(s) = \frac{1,52(12s+1+36s^2)}{12s(1+8s)(1+17s)+1,52(12s+1+36s^2)} \quad (8)$$

3. Results and discussions

To study the transfer function properties it is introduced in Matlab and is introduced the command [z,p,k]=tf2zpk(num,den), where num and den are the transfer function numerator and denominator. This command gives:

z = 0; -0.0437 + 0.0725i; -0.0437 - 0.0725i
 p = -0.1299; -0.1667 + 0.0000i; -0.1667 - 0.0000i;
 k = 0.0335,

where: z are the system zeroes; p – the system poles; k – the gain factor.

The following conclusions are extracted: the transfer function, $H_0(s)$ is strictly proper; the numerator and denominator polynomials are Hurwitz polynomials because their roots are placed in the left half pane, so the system is stable; the numerator and denominator polynomials are compress so the system is irreducible and has minimal dimension; the

system described by $H_0(s)$ is completely controllable and observable.

In Figure 1 is presented the automatic control scheme described by the transfer function, the PID regulator and the perturbation given by the walls isolation and the heat produced by the stored fruits and vegetables. The isolation is described by a sinusoidal function in which the amplitude is given by the exterior maximal temperature minus the exterior minimal temperature and the frequency by the time elapsed between two consecutive temperature extreme values. The heat produced by stored fruits and vegetables is reproduced by a ramp function, which has a ramp established in function of specialized literature data which presents the produced heat distribution during storage.

Use clear ideas, short sentences, and standard terminology. Special characters, symbols, and measure units must comply with the standards in use.

Fig.1 Automatic control scheme

The perturbation and the automatic control system output representations are presented in Figures 2,3 and 4. This simulation is made

for a 86 400 sec duration (1 day), in which the outside temperature has a 15°C variation.

Fig. 2. The perturbation form given by the outside temperature variation

Fig.3. The perturbation form given by the heat produced by fruits and vegetables

Fig. 4. The automatic temperature adjustment output when a ramp input is applied

Fig.5. The control system output without using a PID regulator

As it can be observed from this figures, when is applied a step input (can be represented by the set of a new temperature to which the fruits and vegetables will be stored) over the temperature automatic adjustment system, the proposed control system is compensating very well the perturbations which actions over this system. Also it enters very quickly from transitory regime to stationary regime (100 s). The oscillations

observed in figure 4 are between 0.992...0.995, so the system comportment is optimal.

In figure 5 is presented the automatic system comportment without a PID regulator attached to the control loop. As it can be observed the warehouse inside temperature is oscillating sinusoidal in function of the exterior temperature but with a easy tendency of growing due to the perturbation given by the heat produced by stored fruits and vegetables

4. Conclusions

1. Fruits and vegetables storage has a major economical importance for fruits and vegetables producers because they can assure a continue flow of fresh products on the market, not being conditioned by fruits and vegetables perish.

2. This proposed control system offers a quick response to a new input, reaching the stationary regime in about 100 sec. Also the perturbations are not affecting the system stability, the output

remaining between 0.992...0.995 through the simulation.

3. Perfecting automatic temperature control systems can be achieved by finding the mathematical model which describes the physical phenomenon which take place inside the warehouse cell and then by passing this model into Laplace domain and implementing this model into simulation software

Papers are written electronically, using a word-processing application.

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HOMOROD – BRAȘOV COUNTY – A FORGOTTEN TOURISTIC DESTINATION

M. FLOREA*

Abstract. A Saxon village located in NE Brasov County has an important touristic value due to a unique fortified church. Homorod was also a spa established more than 100 years ago but forgotten during communism and completely destroyed today. In this village was also a study for Lipizzaner horses which is in a process of developing. In order to increase the touristic potential the spa area needs to be reconstructed and the muddy volcanoes nearby to be protected.

Key words: Homorod, fortified citadel, spa, muddy volcanoes.

Located in an interior subcarpathic depression, in NW basaltic area of The PerșaniMountaines, Homorod is a crossroad between Brașov, Rupea (on E 60 road) and OdorheiuSecuiesc. The name comes from the Saxon words: *hom* meaning height or hill and *roden* which means cutting the forest. This name is also present for two villages in Alba and Sălaj Counties but much better is known for Homorod Spa in Harghita County.

Dating from the 13 th century, the village from the northern part of the Brașov County, has been founded by the Saxons colonized by Hungarian King Bella II in order to protect eastern Transylvania from Turkish and Tartarian invasions. The so called "landen" came from Rhein-Moselle region and were supposed to erect citadels for defense purposes. The first location was on the Mill Hill, where now is the orthodox cemetery but later they erected a huge fortified church near the Homorod River where actually is the village center. The first name of the village was Petersdorf (after the name of the church) but later was called Homorod due to the cuttings of the forests.

The main touristic attraction is the fortified church called St. Peter which was recently renovated. The evangelic church has the oldest wall paintings of gothic style in Transylvania, the main theme is called Majestas Domini, God being surround by the four evangelists. It has also a good organ, nice interior paintings and huge

walls in the middle of which dominates a big bell tower. From the top you can see for miles and notice the old mechanism of the clock. Nearby is the school with an old hall used for cultural purposes, mainly for performances and for the brassbandsrehearhals. The village use to have three Germanbrassbands and a Romanian one.

The former Homorod Spa was located at 474 m altitude 3 km east from the village, near the

forested area of the PerșaniMountaines. It had a large promenade of fur trees bath facilities, restaurants, rooms for rent kiosk for the

In order to understand the value of the mineral waters there is a chemical analysis realized in 1933 by two professors from Chemistry Faculty of the Bucharest University:

NaCl.....	18.1004
Fe(HCO ₃) ₂	0.0018
KCl.....	0.0708
Mg(HCO ₃) ₂	0.0915
LiCl.....	0.0013
H ₃ BO ₃	0.450
CINH ₄	0.214
H ₂ SiO ₃	0.213
NaI.....	0.0002

The average water volumes were about 250 m³/day provided by two centrifugal water pumps. These mineral waters were suitable for rheumatism.

Na ₂ SO ₄	0.9192
NaHCO ₂	2.6379
Ca(HCO ₃) ₂ ...	0.2893
Mg(HCO ₃) ₂ ..	0.2078

Besides the waters there were used therapeutic muds rich in sulphur, organic substances, iron and calcium oxides and fine grain sand consisting of former basaltic lava. The high time of the Homorod Spa was between the two World Wars, when many people used the facilities of the spa. During communism the spa was nationalized, the

Saxon owner committed suicide and the activity decreased till the complete failure. The native gipsy population destroyed the bath

brassbands. The mineral waters from here were well known in the whole country so Homorod use to have a railway station.

chambers, the installations even cut the fur tree promenade.

The only interesting place to visit is a small plateau with muddy volcanoes, which now is a protected area. Their existence is connected with the methane doms from the Transylvanian Plateau, which due to its pressure brings the underground mineral waters through a layer of clay and sands forming a mud full of mineral and organic substances.

On the entrance from Rupea Railway Station there are stables for horses which were famous in the past. More than 100 lipizzaner horses were bred and they were well known in whole Europe. After the revolution the stables were bought by a private investor who finally abandoned the horses. They were almost dead from starvation but the local authorities saved them.

We consider that this spa could revive with the implications of local and regional authorities and together with the nice preserved fortified church would be an interesting touristic attraction in this isolated area of the Brasov County.

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THE CUSTOMER PERCEPTION OF TOURISM SERVICES QUALITY

D.M. DĂNILĂ G. DĂNILĂ L. GACEU

Abstract: *The papers presents the importance of tourism services quality for customer perception as well as an online measurement system for assessing the quality of transport tourism services, based on customer's survey.*

Keywords : *quality, service, tourism, customer, rates*

1. Introduction

According to Ying Lee " Service is a very important part of every aspect of daily living . It is especially related to the hospitality industry which is based on service. The quality of that service is of critical importance because good service may win customers and poor quality will lose them. Tourism is a major part of the hospitality industry and is a very competitive business. Competitors may have equal facilities, clever advertising, or reasonable prices, but without a strong service commitment success is difficult. Service excellence springs from leadership and organizational culture. It is invaluable asset which cannot be purchased in any store "[4].

2. Service Quality is What Customers Perceive

In a tourism course written by Oğuz Benice is stated that " In the tourism industry, we deal mainly with services, not goods. Sometimes it is difficult at times to describe these services, know where to purchase them, or even make distinctions between services and goods. The distinctions may at times become blurred become some tourism organizations are involved primarily in the delivery of services while others deliver both services and goods [3]. Services provided by these and other tourism organizations are called "intangibles" since they cannot be placed in inventories and pulled out of warehouses or off of shelves like a can of beans or a compact disk [3]. Services are not only intangible but they are also highly perishable. Tourism services perish or lose their value with the passage of time just like fresh fruits and vegetables that eventually spoil and must be thrown away [3]. Think about the airplane that has just left the gate, the cruise ship that has just been pushed away from the dock, or the

fireworks show that marks the end of a concert. In each of these situations, the opportunity to generate revenue from the seat, cabin, or concert has disappeared forever [3]. Services are also different from goods because they are actions performed by one person on behalf of another. Sometimes we are merely the recipients of services but, at other times, we become actively involved in the service delivery process. " [3].

Another appreciation regarding to customer and perceived services is made by Ying Lee "Only the customer can assess the quality of service and perceived service. Service quality cannot be separated from what a customer received and how services were performed. What the customer received is the technical or outcome dimension. How the services were performed and delivered was the functional or process-related dimension, when customers go to hotels, restaurants, airports and banks, they will receive rooms, meals, transportation and financial services. All of these are technical or outcomes of the operations and are part of the service experience"[4].

In Oğuz Benice opinion : " How the service delivery functions is critical to the perceptions of service quality. The behavior of waiters, bank tellers, travel agency representatives, bus drivers and how these service employees perform their tasks also influence the customer's view of the service. Most of us probably think of quality as synonymous with "excellence." Technically, from a management and marketing perspective, quality represents a form of measurement like a thermometer or ruler. Products have some amount of quality: we talk of high quality or bad quality, good quality or poor quality. Quality is both objective and subjective in nature. Objectively, we can measure some aspects of quality because they involve objective, or measurable, amounts of certain attributes or ingredients [3]. A spacious hotel room would be

rated as higher quality than a smaller one simply based on the measurable dimensions of the two rooms. Likewise, a flight that takes off on time and arrives ahead of schedule would be thought of as higher in quality than a late flight, based on the quantifiable aspect of time as measured in minutes. However, this measurable concept of quality is not the complete picture of quality. Much of quality is subjective—in the "eye of the beholder. [3]"

In addition to these objective versus subjective concepts of quality is the idea of value. The value-based definition of quality incorporates the notion of a trade-off; the trade-off between service attributes and service performance with the price paid for the quality received. Even if you are an infrequent flyer, you no doubt have recognized the objective quality differences between first or business class and coach. In first class, passengers sit in leather-covered, spacious "lounger"-style seats with more leg room between the rows. In addition, they receive bountiful amounts of food and beverages served on fine china. But do you believe the quality received in first class is worth the difference in price? "[3].

3. Online customer evaluation for the transport service quality received

The travel word is a keyword in tourism definition. Just as there are different types of visitors, there are different forms and categories of travel which take place, varying by traveler, destination, and motive for travel, such as international vs. domestic travel, intra-regional vs. interregional travel, as well as inbound vs. outbound travel [1].

In the most of the cases travel implies transport services. If the customer flies to its vacation destination, bringing the personal car is not an option. Some areas have public transportation that can be used, but getting a taxi service every time when the client wants to go out can be very expensive. The best option to solve the transport problem is to rent a car. In the most of the cases the tourist uses the Internet to find a car rental supplier. For this purpose a reservation on the profile website is made. The website is the front office client interface. The reservations are processed further by an online reservation management which is the back office interface. The quality of the transport services provided by the website www.eurocars.ro based on customer ratings was analyzed in this paper. EuroCars is the Romanian online leader in providing tourist transport services. The services provided are: car rental with or without driver, minibuses and limousines rental.

Online quality survey.

This survey form is important for us in the attempt to constantly improve the quality of our services.

Question	very poor		average		excellent
1. Finding the car rental agent at your destination	<input type="radio"/>				
2. The standard and helpfulness of the agent	<input type="radio"/>				
3. The time it took to get your rental car	<input type="radio"/>				
4. The quality of the rental car	<input type="radio"/>				
5. How clean the car was	<input type="radio"/>				
6. Service when returning the car	<input type="radio"/>				
7. The car was according to the description?	<input type="radio"/>				
8. The overall service provided by the car rental supplier	<input type="radio"/>				
9. Would you rent a car from Eurocars.ro again?	<input type="radio"/>				

Other comments or suggestions:

Total Rating: 0.00

Finish

Fig. 1. Online quality survey

The quality of services offered to tourists by EuroCars partners were obtained using an online graphical interface graphical interface. In this system, customers completed questionnaires and they evaluated by rates the transport service received. When a customer finished the rental service, the online module sends automatically an e-mail to the client. The client is asked to complete an online survey and to assess the quality of the rented service with rates from 1 to 5 . Customer must answer nine questions significant for the service quality provided by supplier as presented in figure 1.

Also some comments can be written by client in a special box from the survey. Once survey is completed is automatically recorded in Eurocars graphical module for each partner. This way EuroCars has the possibility to control the quality of services and intervene where is necessary [2].

In the picture from figure 2 are the results of several companies that offer rental services under the brand EuroCars. The question number was noted with : Q1 ... Q9, and the number of survey for each partner was noted with S

PROVIDER NAME	Nr.S	Q1	Q2	Q3	Q4	Q5	Q6	Q7	Q8	Q9	Total
Active Trade & Marketing Srl	46	4.26	4.26	4.17	3.67	4.26	4.07	3.88	4.07	4.16	4.09
Adras COM IMPEX	43	4.81	4.74	4.67	4.29	4.14	4.64	4.52	4.67	4.55	4.56
Anita ProdimpeX	77	4.68	4.64	4.68	4.08	4.51	4.62	4.43	4.52	4.68	4.54
Apirent SRL	26	3.92	4.38	4.27	4.15	4.46	4.15	4.27	4.23	4.08	4.21
Autonom Bacau	38	4.45	4.47	4.50	3.55	4.13	4.39	4.05	4.16	4.26	4.22
Easy Car Service	46	4.63	4.61	4.59	4.20	4.50	4.54	4.48	4.46	4.50	4.50
Prima EXIM	159	4.20	4.30	4.11	3.61	3.75	4.10	4.13	4.03	4.04	4.03
In Front Cars SRL	66	4.55	4.56	4.36	4.06	4.18	4.32	4.62	4.29	4.38	4.37

Fig. 2. Clients assessment

Question number 4 regarding the quality of the rental car had the smallest rates, and question number 2, regarding the standard and helpfulness of the agent obtained the biggest rates. The fact that the car quality is not very well perceived by the customer is not a surprise. There are at list two factors that leads to this quality perception : cars are involved in rental activity with all the consequences and also are used on Romanian roads not all the time in good condition.

4. Conclusions

All in all it is very important for organizations to determine exactly what customers expect in order to improve the services in this direction . "Dissatisfied customers are a slow, silent killer. They defect one by one, often without making a sound. What's worse, they often bring other customers or potential customers down with them - slowly, silently and viciously. Luckily, there is a way to give voice to this otherwise silent

majority and fix many problems before they cause customers to defect: customer satisfaction surveys."

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RESEARCH REGARDING FRESH CUT FRUIT AND VEGETABLE TEXTURE

L.G. CIULICĂ*

Abstract: *Fresh-cut vegetable and fruit products differ from traditional, intact vegetables and fruits in terms of their physiology and their handling requirements. Fresh-cut vegetables deteriorate faster than intact produce. This is a direct result of the wounding associated with processing, which leads to a number of physical and physiological changes affecting the viability and quality of the produce.*

Keywords: *cutting, texture, vegetables, fruits.*

1. Introduction

The limitation or even avoidance of the defects of mechanical origin that may affect fruit quality can be achieved only by knowing the physical and mechanical properties and behavior of the various types of their mechanical requests. Based on their knowledge can be made useful recommendations for appropriate design and choice of packaging according to the category of fruits, the degree of maturation and duration and conditions of storage (storage). Therefore took place and continues to conduct numerous theoretical and experimental researches on this properties and behavior to various types of mechanical requests of the fruits, the factors which affects them, their correlations with the tissue and cellular chemical composition. [1]

In reference to fruits and vegetables, the characteristics that impart distinctive quality may be described by four different attributes—1) color and appearance, 2) flavor (taste and aroma), 3) texture and 4) nutritional value.

As consumers, these four attributes typically affect us in the order specified above, for example we evaluate the visual appearance and color first, followed by the taste, aroma, and texture. [2]

2. Fruit and vegetable texture

Textural parameters of fruits and vegetables are perceived with the sense of touch, either when the product is picked up by hand or placed in the mouth and chewed. In contrast to flavor

attributes, these characteristics are fairly easily measured using instrumental methods.

Most plant materials contain a significant amount of water and other liquid-soluble materials surrounded by a semi-permeable membrane and cell wall. The texture of fruits and vegetables is derived from their turgor pressure, and the composition of individual plant cell walls and the middle lamella “glue” that holds individual cells together. Cell walls are composed of cellulose, hemicellulose, pectic substances, proteins, and in the case of vegetables, lignin.

Tomatoes are an example of a fruit vegetable that is approximately 93–95% water and 5–7% total solids, the latter comprised of roughly 80–90% soluble and 10–20% insoluble solids. The greatest contributor to the texture of tomato products are the insoluble solids, which are derived from cell walls. The three-dimensional network of plant cell walls is still unresolved, but is a topic of great interest to scientists in that to a large degree it dictates the perception of consistency, smoothness, juiciness etc. in fruit and vegetable tissues.

According to Bourne (1982) the textural properties of a food are the “group of physical characteristics that arise from the structural elements of the food, are sensed by the feeling of touch, are related to the deformation, disintegration and flow of the food under a force, and are measured objectively by functions of mass, time, and distance.” The terms texture, rheology, consistency, and viscosity are often used interchangeably, despite the fact that they describe properties that are somewhat different. In practice the term texture is used primarily with

* Dept. of Food Engineering, Transilvania University of Braşov, Romania, e-mail: laura_georgiana1@yahoo.com

reference to solid or semi-solid foods; however, most fruits and vegetables are viscoelastic, implying that they exhibit combined properties of ideal liquids, which demonstrate only viscosity (flow), and ideal solids, which exhibit only elasticity (deformation). [2]

In general, perishability of intact fruits and vegetables correlates well with respiration rates; produce with a high respiration rate tends to be more perishable. In fresh cut products, as a result of wounding, respiration is elevated compare to the intact products. Moreover, the extent of wounding also affects the shelf-life of products.

Saltveit states that the immediate physical effects of wounding tissue, such as what occurs during peeling or size reduction operations, are to cause mechanical stress to the tissue, to remove the protective epidermal layer, to accumulate surface moisture, and to expose tissue to contaminants. Dramatic changes in gas diffusion occur with tissue wounding, and as moisture at the cut surface evaporates, additional changes in diffusion occur. [2]

Fresh cut products tend to be more vulnerable to water losses because they are no longer intact after peeling and cutting or shredding, slicing, etc. Peel or skin is a very important barrier to loss of turgor and desiccation; many commodities have a protective waxy coating, highly resistant to water loss. Evidently, peel removal renders commodities more perishable. The mechanical injury brought on by cutting and the method used, directly expose the internal tissues to the atmosphere, promoting desiccation. The shredding or slicing operations result in increased surface area, an additional problem. Moreover, mechanical injury brings about physiological responses, such as respiration increase and potentially ethylene production, responses that shorten the life of a commodity.

Processing operations such as washing, scrubbing, peeling, trimming, cutting, shredding, etc carried out during the initial stages of fresh-cut preparation cause mechanical injury to the plant tissues. During peeling and cutting operations if the equipment used is not in the best conditions, for example if dull knives and blades are used, bruising and damage occurs in more tissue layers than intended, thus the sharpness of knife blades can significantly affect product storage life. [3]

Fresh-cut vegetable and fruit products differ from traditional, intact vegetables and fruits in

terms of their physiology and their handling requirements. Fresh-cut vegetables deteriorate faster than intact produce. This is a direct result of the wounding associated with processing, which leads to a number of physical and physiological changes affecting the viability and quality of the produce. The visual symptoms of deterioration of fresh-cut produce include flaccidity from loss of water, changes in color (especially increased oxidative browning at the cut surfaces), and microbial contamination. Nutrient losses may also be accelerated when plant tissues are wounded. Little information is available concerning the retention of vitamins and minerals, and other nutritive components in fresh-cut produce during handling, storage, and senescence. [4]

3. Material and method

Instrumental or objective methods of texture evaluation can be grouped into three classes: fundamental, empirical, and imitative tests. Fundamental tests measure properties that are familiar to engineers, e.g. strength, Poisson's ratio, and various modules such as Young's modulus, Shear modulus, and Bulk modulus (Bourne, 1982). Empirical tests cover a wide range of simple and rapid tests, including puncture, compression, extrusion, shear, and others, which measure one or more textural properties and are commonly used in quality control applications. Most methods used for the evaluation of the textural properties of fruits and vegetables are empirical or semi-empirical. Finally, imitative tests are those which utilize instruments in an attempt to mimic what occurs in the mouth as the food is masticated. Experience teaches us that these empirical and imitative tests correlate well with sensory judgments, but we usually have little or no fundamental understanding of the test.

The most commonly used methods for the evaluation of textural properties are those which apply large deforming forces (e.g. via puncture or compression) and are therefore destructive.

Because of the empirical nature of these tests, however, they do not provide us with an understanding of food microstructure or force-deformation and failure mechanisms at the cellular level. [2]

There is no economy in operating any cutting machine with dull or unserviceable knives. The

cost of lost time and product waste far exceeds the cost of knife maintenance and replacement. Even the sharpest of knives cause a small amount of cell rupture in the product, but dull knives can cause an even greater amount of cell rupture, resulting in reduced yield and quality. Processors cutting foods for dehydration must pay particular attention to knife sharpness as it is extremely important that nutrients remain in the cells until the product is dried.

It is an established fact that very few products can be “cut” in the true sense that the sharp edge of a knife is always in contact with the product. A sharp edge is most useful in its ability to penetrate the product cleanly to start the cut. Beyond this point, most materials tend to split or separate some distance ahead the edge. Thick knives or blunt edge bevels increase splitting and cause loss of cutting control. Thin knives with slender edge bevels allow the knife to enter the product gently, guiding the path of the “split” more accurately.

Every knife becomes a compromise between the ideal edge shape for efficient cutting, and the mechanical strength necessary for practical use.

Knowledge about the response of fruit and vegetables from the application of different types of loads, is the description of material properties, and is used to determine resistance against injuries to transport agricultural products, processing, storage, and as consumers.

Most food stands in terms of flow behavior between the two extremes, Newtonian fluids and elastic solids. At low strain rates all material behaves predominantly viscous elasticity can be omitted. At high strain rate situation is reversed.

In rheometry there are two types of experimental tests:

- creep test (slow flow), which corresponds to the application of effort, registration and measurement of strain γ .
- relaxation test (back), which corresponds to the application of strain, measurement and registration effort τ .

Apparent effect in this case depends on strain rate, which means that the flow of fluid that leaves the cells is crucial. Apple tissue differs from that of the potatoes and carrots by the much higher number of intracellular locations, with approximately 20%. In the case of apples, spaces are filled with gas which is easily compressible. During distortion, neighboring cells can expand freely in these spaces and, in this case, the current size of the gap decreases. Therefore, in the transverse plane 2D deformation cell size increases and decreases the amount of space. [5]

Fruit and vegetable quality is comprised of four primary attributes, 1 - color and appearance, 2 - flavor (taste and aroma), 3 - texture and 4 - nutritional value. These attributes have been defined, and may be evaluated as either sensory or instrumental measurements, or preferably a

combination of the two. Sensory measurement are generally more useful in the development of new products and determining product standards while instrumental methods are superior in measuring quality on a routine basis. There are advantages and disadvantages to both types of measurements, and one should use appropriate methods with potential limitations in mind. The effects of various unit operations on the quality of fresh-cut products was reviewed, and it was noted that there has been more attention paid in the literature to the effects of cutting operations, packaging, and modified atmosphere storage than other operations. Since these operations are most likely to adversely affect quality, this focus and prioritization seemed appropriate. Investigators have determined that some simple instrumental measurements of color (hue, chroma, the L value, and the whiteness index), soluble solids, changes in weight or juice leakage, and the ascorbate content (as an indicator of nutritional value) may be used as indices of quality changes in fresh-cut fruits and vegetables. [2]

4. Conclusions

In the models developed by Pitt (1982) and Pitt and Chen (1983), the compression causes lateral extension of cells due to incompressibility of intracellular fluid. Assuming that it does not move outside the cell, cell volume remains constant during deformation. It causes much more extensive application of cell walls that are transverse to the direction of force than the cell wall in the longitudinal direction of the force being in stress. If the plan of survey will be transverse to the direction of deformation, it is expected that cells located in the plan to grow in size, similar to Ulmeda and Zdunek's

experimental observations (2006) made of potatoes and carrots using a confocal microscope laser.

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CURRENT ISSUES REGARDING THE CONDITIONING OF BLUEBERRY AND RASPBERRY FRUITS IN OZONATED ATMOSPHERE FOR CONSUMPTION AND CONSERVATION

C.C. FLOREA *

GH. BRĂTUCU**

Abstract: This paper presents the factors which affect the berries' alteration and which favor their qualitative depreciation, with applications to blueberries and raspberries. In light of these elements and the active principles content of blueberries and raspberries, inhibiting or destroying possibilities for biological agents (microorganisms) and removing other polluting factors in order to maintain their quality until they reach the final consumers or industrial processing plants are analyzed. It appears that the metabolic reactions involved in the development of micro-organisms in berries depend on both the chemical composition of the substrate, temperature and the presence of oxygen. We propose a method and a device for treating these fruits using an ozonated atmosphere.

Keywords: blueberry, raspberry, conditioning, ionization, conservation.

1. Introduction

Due to climatic conditions and geographical position, Romania has a rich and varied spontaneous flora. Berries valued as forest products accessories are considered organic products, are not affected by pollution and they're not treated with chemical fertilizer or pest controllers. Berries are popular because of their taste, specific flavor, special nutritional and therapeutic effects. The problem regarding conserving these fruits is current, researchers being preoccupied with finding modern and more economical methods of conservation that do not affect the organoleptic and chemical properties.

The therapeutic and nutritional value of berries on the human body is due to the active principles contained in fruits or leaves. The composition of each plant consists of numerous chemical compounds which have to be identified in order to highlight their pharmacological action.

Food and therapeutic aspects of the blueberry and raspberry bush are found in a list that impresses not only by size, but through the effect of these foods - drugs or, rather, medicine - foods, that make herbal research subjects.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. The materials studied in this paper are fruits and leaves from blueberries and raspberries, which are presented below.

Blueberry (*Vaccinium myrtillus L.*) is a part of the Ericaceae family and is an undergrowth of about 50cm that grows from the lower limit of spruce stands up to the alpine area and is found throughout the Carpathian chain, especially on shaded and wet slopes. It requires humic podzolic soils that are ferruginous, brown and strongly acidic. It presents shallow and very dense roots that are interwoven, branched stems, round leaves – oval to elliptic, small solitary pale pink globose flowers (fig. 2), spherical dark-blue fruits that are juicy and have a sweet and sour taste.

Fig. 1. Blueberry (*Vaccinium myrtillus L.*)

The species originate in North America and East Asia. Many generations of Native Americans gathered blueberries in the forest, being the first ones to conserve and use them for both their

therapeutical properties and for food. The leaves were used for tea and it was believed that they purified the blood.

The use of blueberry fruit is mentioned as early as the twelfth century, and the interest in this extremely valuable fruit because of its therapeutical and nutritional properties increased with the discovery of its effects on vascular microcirculation and visual acuity.

Chemical composition:

- **Fruit:** tannin, antocianozide, pectins, sugars, provitamin A, vitamin C, organic acids (citric, malic, oxalic, succinic, lactic), mucilage, flavonoids, izocumarine.
- **Leaves:** tannin, arbutin, hydroquinone, myrtilin and neomyrtilin.

The chemical composition of blueberry fruits is presented in table 1 [4].

Fig. 2. Blueberry flower

Table 1

Chemical composition of blueberry fruits

Chemical composition	Fruits
Water	86%
Sugars	7...13%
Sucrose	1...2%
Ash	0.45...0.50%
Proteins	0.8...1.2%
Organic acids	circa 1% (benzoic, tartaric, malic, citric)
Pectic substances	0.35...0.49%
Tannin	0.3...0.43%
Vitamins	Vitamin C 12...30 mg%; Vitamin A 280 I.U. Vitamin PP 0.2 mg%; Vitamin B ₁ (thiamine) 0.02 mg% Vitamin B ₂ (riboflavin) 0.02 mg% Vitamin E 2.29 mg%
Mineral salts	Potassium 50 mg%; Calcium 10 mg%; Phosphorus 8 mg%; Sulfur 8 mg%; Magnesium 6 mg%; Chlorine 5 mg%; Manganese 3 mg%; Iron 1 mg%

A comparative study conducted in Hill Laboratories in New Zealand in 2007 shows that blueberries from spontaneous flora (*Vaccinium myrtillosum* L.) contain active principles in larger

quantities than growing blueberries (*Vaccinium corymbosum*). The results of this study are presented in the tables 2 and 3 [5].

Table 2

Content of main vitamins in growing blueberries and spontaneous flora blueberries

Content of main vitamins in growing blueberries and spontaneous flora blueberries	Growing blueberries <i>Vaccinium corymbosum</i>	Spontaneous flora blueberries <i>Vaccinium myrtillosum</i> L.
Vitamin A in I.U./kg	850	1000
Vitamin B ₁ (thiamine) in mg/kg	0.2	0.2
Vitamin B ₂ (riboflavin) in mg/kg	0.2	0.2
Vitamin PP (niacin) in mg/kg	3	4
Vitamin C (ascorbic acid) in mg/kg	220	250

Table 3

Content of main mineral substances in growing blueberries (*Vaccinum corymbosum*) and spontaneous flora blueberries (*Vaccinum myrtillus* L.)

Content of main mineral substances in growing blueberries and spontaneous flora blueberries	Growing blueberries <i>Vaccinum corymbosum</i>	Spontaneous flora blueberries <i>Vaccinum myrtillus</i> L.
Calcium in mg/kg	80	210
Magnesium in mg/kg	58	80
Potassium in mg/kg	910	990
Sodium in mg/kg	<10	<10
Phosphorus in mg/kg	120	180
Copper in mg/kg	0.42	0.77
Iron in mg/kg	3	3.6
Manganese in mg/kg	4.6	47
Zinc in mg/kg	0.81	1.4

Blueberry is a raw material for food industry, pharmaceutical industry and biotherapy, using both the fruit (*Fructus Myrtilli*) and the leaves (*Folium Myrtilli*).

Raspberry (*Rubus idaeus*) of the Rosaceae family (fig. 3) is a bushy shrub with creeping sprouts widely found in forest areas in mountainous regions, but also in forests and rocky coastlines. It grows on moderately acidic soils that are humus-rich and loose. It has a branched, shallow root (10...30 cm), erect stems, arched at the top, simple or branched, cylindrical, high up to 1,5...2,0 m, with a barbed bottom, odd leaves cu 3...5, rarely 7 leaflets – in the shape of a lance, whitish on the back, small white flowers, grouped and red fruit (fig. 4), with a diameter between 13...20 mm, aromatic and sweet [3].

Fig. 4. Raspberry fruit

There are two main species of raspberry, the spontaneous flora and the one cultivated in different varieties. So far over 40 varieties of cultures are known, 9 being approved in the official catalog of growing plant species for 2010.

Rubus idaeus is also known as the European raspberry and was originally from Asia and brought to Europe. It began to be cultivated since the sixteenth century. The special quality of raspberries, as a result of Romanian specific climatic conditions has made this fruit to be increasingly requested in export.

Raspberry leaves and stems are used for medicinal purposes to prepare tea which prevents diarrhoea, dysentery, angina and tonsillitis. In addition to the consumption of fresh fruits they are used in the food and, pharmaceuticals industries and biotherapy.

Chemical composition:

- **Fruits:** sugars, tannins, pectin, provitamin A, vitamin C, organic acids, carbonic acid, minerals and proteins.

Fig. 3. Raspberry (*Rubus idaeus*)

- **Leaves:** 10% tannins, substances related to flavones, vitamin C 800 mg%, minerals and micronutrients.

The chemical composition of raspberries' fruits is shown in table 4 [4].

Table 4

Chemical composition of raspberries' fruits

Chemical composition	Fruits
<i>Water</i>	85...86%
<i>Sugars</i>	4.5...10 g%
<i>Pectin</i>	0.5...2.8 g%
<i>Ash</i>	0.6 g%
<i>Proteins</i>	1.2 g%
<i>Organic acids</i>	1.0...2.3 g% (citric, malic, oxalic)
<i>Carbonic acid</i>	25 mg%
<i>Vitamins</i>	Vitamin C 30 mg% Provitamin A in small quantities Vitamin D in small quantities Vitamin P in small quantities Vitamin B ₁ (thiamine) 0.02 mg% Vitamin B ₂ (riboflavin) 0.03 mg% Vitamin E 2.29 mg%
<i>Mineral salts</i>	Potassium 127 mg%; Calcium 27.3 mg%; Phosphorus 45 mg%; Copper 1 mg%; Magnesium 24 mg%; Chlorine 5 mg%; Manganese 15 mg%; Iron 0.6 mg%; Sodium 3.5 mg%; Zinc 3 mg%;

Laboratory investigations have established that in the vast majority of cases, the quantity of active principles is not the same in all organs of a plant, and the quantitative and qualitative stability over time depends on the conditions of preserving of this plant product. Harvested fruits continue to live, and while being preserved, their chemical structure and quality change due to biochemical processes, the most obvious of which are aerobic and anaerobic respiration. Also, due to external factors (light, heat and humidity of the environment) physical changes will occur. Breathing is an oxidation, produced under the influence of air oxygen (aerobic respiration), which divides sugars into CO₂ and H₂O based on the following chemical reaction:

During this process the fruit is heated in order to help water evaporate, thus causing "fruit sweating." By increasing temperature, the breathing process intensifies, causing the loss of organic substances (sugars, acids, pectin).

Another biochemical process that leads to deterioration of the fruits is anaerobic respiration, which occurs when air is absent or present in small quantities. Sugars divide into alcohol and CO₂ under the action of zimas and the process

of alcoholic fermentation occurs. The chemical reaction is as follows:

Alcoholic fermentation occurs at temperatures between 15°C and 30°C and below 5°C and over 50°C, the process stops. After this process the browning of fruit tissues follows, and cells die [2].

2.2. Conditioning methods and procedures for preserving blueberries and raspberries

One factor for obtaining good quality material is the optimum time of harvest, which is conditioned by the length of the fruit growing season, time of day and weather conditions during harvest. Being highly perishable due to high water content and tissue fragility, the optimal duration of storage the raspberries and blueberries after harvest and under favorable conditions of temperature and relative humidity is 2...3 days.

Using microscopic examination, the fungus that causes blueberries and raspberries impairment of quality can be identified. Microorganisms that contribute to alteration of berries are microscopic fungi (molds and yeasts) and bacteria. Molds of the genera *Botrytis*, *Rhizopus*, *Mucor*, *Aspergillus*, *Penicillium* and *Cladosporium* can

cause alterations of berries. Bacteria are microorganisms with a high power of alteration, with an increased rate of proliferation, some of them being powerful toxins [2].

- In order to reduce the berries' metabolism and suppress the development of pathogens, the research conducted so far has shown that **rapid cooling of fruits while maintaining a temperature of 0°C**, the optimum storage temperature of blueberries and raspberries can be achieved by refrigeration. This method of conservation, based on the principle of anabiosis, has the advantage of reducing the intensity of breath and prevents the ripening process. A disadvantage of this method is that it only has an effect on stopping the proliferation of microorganisms, and not the elimination of them. Another disadvantage considering the economic reasons is that in the vast majority of cases, specific costs increase with cooling rate.

- Removing fungi, bacteria, and other elements such as organic or inorganic impurities from blueberries and raspberries can be achieved using **nonthermal conservation methods: ionizing radiation, ultraviolet radiation and ultrashort pulses of light**.

- **The ionizing γ radiation** used to destroy microorganisms is electromagnetic radiation (photons) and is characterized by wavelength $\lambda \cong 0.01 \mu\text{m}$. For disinfecting fresh berries, doses of 0.15..0.50 kGy are used, and for the elimination of microorganisms doses of 1..6 kGy are used. The main disadvantage of using ionizing γ radiation at doses above 4 kGy is the partial

destruction of the active principles contained in the blueberries and raspberries, mainly vitamins, vitamin C being the most sensitive, followed by vitamins B1, B6, B12, PP, A, E and K and the loss of vitamins comparable to that of thermal sterilization.

- **Ultraviolet radiation** used in food industry for preserving fruit are electromagnetic, with the wavelength $\lambda = 240 \text{ nm}$ and have a strong bactericidal and germicidal power. The lethal effect depends on the dose of irradiation ($\mu \text{ W/cm}^2$) and irradiation time (*seconds*). The action sterilizing unit is expressed by U, which represents the action of a dose of $10 \mu \text{ W/cm}^2$ for 60 seconds. It has the advantage of low penetrating power, unchanging the chemical components sensitive to UV-C radiation, the inner layers below 0.1 mm being unharmed by the UV radiation.

- **Ultrashort pulses of light** produced by the laser generator or "flash" generators lamps may cause destruction of microorganisms on the surface of fruit. By applying ultrashort pulses of light on refrigerated or frozen fruits, an extension of their shelf-life can be obtained [1].

The innovative solution which is planned to be implemented within the doctoral thesis is the design and implementation of equipment that destroys microorganisms by the use of ozone produced by Corona discharge. The scheme of the cold sterilization equipment for berries by ozone is shown in figure 5.

Fig. 5. The scheme of the cold sterilization equipment for berries by ozone

The efficiency increase of the equipment is due to the principle of producing ozone, even at the surface of the metal conveyor belt, close to the fruits that are treated. By providing optimal

distance between the Corona discharge space and the moving conveyor surface on which the fruits will be treated using this new technology, an increase in the electric field strength and with it an increase in the electrical power that generates ozone will be obtained.

Berries situated on the metal link chain conveyor 1 are uniformly distributed in a single layer over its surface. They are led to the metal plate 2 that is coupled to the plus of the high voltage generator (30 kV). Since the conveyor is coupled to the minus of the source, ozone will be generated on its surface due to the Corona effect 5. The metal plate 2 is fixed to the chassis through the insulation board 4. The dielectric 3 does not allow direct discharges from the anode to the cathode, but only to produce the Corona effect.

3. Conclusions

✓ Maintaining the qualitative value of blueberries and raspberries from harvesting to consumption or industrial processing is linked to their biological nature and the conditions under which they are stored. Based on these preliminary data it is proposed to study the effect of berry destroying microorganisms, by using the ozone produced by Corona discharge.

✓ Due to high water content and tissue fragility, and being highly perishable, the shelf

life of cranberry and blueberries can be increased by treating them with ozone.

✓ The constructive version of cold sterilization of berries is economical in terms of electricity consumption and can be easily included in the chain of industrial processing technology.

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Video Surveillance Novel Method Applied in Environmental Protected Areas

M. MANESCU* L. CRISTEA** D. OLA***

Abstract: The evolution of monitor video systems lead to a new era of camcorders with digital single-lens reflex (DSRL) technology. Digital camcorders have the following characteristics compared with the analog camcorders: low prices, short post processing time and the possibility to create high quality materials. These advantages of the DSLR devices can be successfully used in the filming techniques used for the surveillance of the wildlife from the protected areas.

This article presents a mechanical construction solution for camera guiding device used for the traveling effects during the surveillance filming. The described solution consists of an mechatronic device that includes the mechanical parts and the software implemented on a 8 bits microcontroller. The microcontroller is used to command the displacement actuator that will move the camera with precision and thus making a time-lapse effect.

This filming method can be applied to cameras used to monitor protected areas and habitats, wildlife, recording of crops development or evolution. In all these situations the camera should be moved in a precise way, during a long period of time that can take weeks or months.

Keywords: monitor, video, time-lapse.

1. Introduction

The new trend in the cinema begins to shift more and more to the DSLR camcorders that can offer to the average person the possibility to create video materials of a high quality in a short time and at a short price. The need to grow the performances of the movie effects made possible the appearance of the DSLR technology and make effects such as "traveling" and „time-lapse traveling". Since the classic filming makes the similar effects by using large, heavy and expensive devices, the need arouse to developed smaller devices, more ergonomic, reliable and not so expensive that would allow the average user of DSLR camcorder to achieve the same effects that are made in the filming studios.

The classic traveling effect (fig. 1), named also truck, was made by moving the filming camera on carriage along a rail. This system was composed of a gliding carriage that was moved by an operator and the filming camera was operated by a cameraman. By moving the camera from one side to another it is obtained the traveling right (truck right) or the traveling left (truck left) effect. Another effect was made by

moving the camera towards the subject, effect named as dolly in, or in the case when the camera was moved away from the subject the effect was named dolly out.

The dolly in/out effects is different from the zoom in/out effects as well the traveling right/left effects are different from the pan right-left effects.

Fig. 1 Movement of the camera from left to right without the pan effect.

Another impressive effect that can be made with any type of DSLR camera is the time-lapse picture. In this filming technique the frequency at which the frames are captured (frame rate) is

*Dept. of Mechatronic Advanced System, Transilvania University of Brasov, Romania, e-mail: memanescu@yahoo.ro

** Dept. of Mechatronic Advanced System, Transilvania University of Brasov, Romania, e-mail: lcristea@unitbv.ro

*** Dept. of Engineering and Management in Tourism, Transilvania University of Braşov, e-mail: danielola@yahoo.com.

much smaller than the ones that is used when showing the final movie. When the captured images are shown on a regular speed that time seems to pass by very fast. One example in capturing frames at an 1 second interval and later show the film with a rate of 30 frames per second will give the impression that the presented piece will run 30 times faster than the time required to film it. The time-lapse effect can be considered the reverse effect of the high speed effect.

This effect has the advantage to be created using any type of DSLR device, since every frame that can be made will have the maximum picturing resolution of the camera, and this will out run by far the best camcorder 1080HD (about 2,1 mega pixels). In the table 1 there are presented the standard format for filming respectively the approximated size in mega pixel.

Table 1. Size of format.

Class	Size of the format	Megapixels
Under 5MP	1280x720	720 HD (1 MP)
	1920x1080	1080 HD (2.1 MP)
	2048x1556	2k Cinema (3.2MP)
	2544x1696	4.3MP DSLR
Between 5MP and 10 MP	2880x2048	D16 Video (5.9MP)
	3504x2336	8.2 MP DSLR
	3656x2664	Cineon/DPX (9.7 MP)
Over 10 MP	4368x2912	12.7 MP DSLR
	4096x3112	4k Cinema (12.7 MP)
	4992x3328	16.7 MP DSLR

Using a higher capturing resolution for each frame than the one possible for the showing of the film, permits the adding of supplemental effects for editing such as crop and pan. If the captured frames have 8.2 mps, which is not a high resolution for the DSLR device, they will have to be lowered to the 1080 HD standard resulting in a drop of 55% from the initial size.

This size reduction can be made either by scaling down either by using some post production effects such as zoom or pan.

2. The developed devices and methods of checking

The operation diagram of the studied technical solution is presented in fig 2.

The mechanical part of dolly system includes a industrial linear guide with 1m length. On the dolly is mounted the camera and the stepper motor. The rotation movement from the step motor is converted through transmission in linear displacement with the help of the rack-pulley system. Controller box has 3 buttons that can make possible the adjustment of power on/off, speed and direction.

Fig. 2 Function diagram

Following the requests of the project it was chosen the microcontroller ATmega8 that could provide command for both the step motor used to move the camera on the guide and realize the interface of the user settings. The microcontroller send signal to the L298 integrate circuit that command stepper motor (fig.3).

Fig. 3 Operation diagram of the device.

The first tests were made using the standard solution shown in figure 3, were the microcontroller sends tact and direction signals to the circuit L297. The circuit L297 realizes the command sequence on the inputs of the H bridges from the amplification circuit L298 how's outputs are connected to the two phases of the step motor.

In order to minimize the cabling of the electric assembly the electronic schematic was modified by elimination of the L298 circuit and it's

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